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Methodological Comparison in Genomic-Wide Association Studies for Several Traits in Arabidopsis and Soybean

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ABSTRACT

In genome-wide association studies (GWAS), hundreds of thousands single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) are genotyped for several hundreds of individuals. Usually, only a very smaller subset of these markers is associated with the trait. Existing methods require Bonferroni correction for multiple tests, which often is too conservative when the number of markers is extremely broad. To address this concern, a series of methods have been proposed in previous studies. However, the knowledge about how to select these methods is limited. Five multi-locus GWAS methods (pLARM EB, pKWm EB, mrMLM, FASTmrEMMA and ISIS EM-BLASSO) and one single-locus GWAS method (GEMMA) were evaluated using five traits in *Arabidopsis thaliana*, including LN10, LN16, and LN22 (leaf number at a flowering time at 10 °C, 16 °C, and 22 °C, respectively), fresh and dry weights (FW and DW) and five quantitative traits in Soybean including LR (length of main root), LH (length of hypocotyls), BS (biomass of seedlings), fresh and dry weights of root (FWR and DWR). As a result, 482 SNPs were found to be associated with the above five traits. Among these SNPs detected, sixty-seven (13.9%) SNPs were common across six methods. Around these significantly associated SNPs, sixty-six previously reported genes had been found to be associated with the above five traits. Among these known genes, twelve (18.2%) were common across the five methods. Approximately 10 to 20 % SNPs or genes were common. With the water treatment, LR, LH, FWR, DWR and BS in 286 soybean accessions were measured in 2014 and 2015. These phenotypic values along with 106013 SNPs were

analyzed by the above six methods. As a result, 460 SNPs were found in the two years to be associated with the above five traits. Among these SNPs detected, 159 (34.57%) SNPs were common across various methods. Approximately 35% SNPs were common. With the salt (NaCl) treatment, the above five soybean traits were also measured in 2014 and 2015. These phenotypic values were also analyzed by the above six GWAS approaches. As a result, 718 SNPs were found to be associated with the above five traits. Among these SNPs detected, 189 (26.32%) SNPs were common across six methods. Around these significantly associated SNPs, eighty-three previously reported genes were found to be associated with the above five traits. Among these known genes, ten (12.05%) were common across the five methods. Approximately 12 to 30% SNPs or genes were common.

In summary, approximately 10 to 35 % SNPs or genes were common across the six GWAS methods in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and soybean datasets. It means that GWAS methods are complimentary in nature. Therefore, this study provides evidence that multiple GWAS methods can be adopted simultaneously in real data analysis. These results provide useful information in crop genetics and breeding.

Keywords

genome-wide association study, multi-locus model; GEMMA; mrMLM; FASTmrEMMA; ISIS EM-BLASSO; pLARmEB; *Arabidopsis thaliana*; *Glycine max*.

Introduction

Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have been widely used in the genetic dissection of complex traits in animal and plant breeding. In a genome-wide association study, hundreds of thousands of markers are genotyped for several hundreds of individuals. Usually, only a very minor subset of these markers is associated with the trait. Although several methods have been proposed, the knowledge about how to select these approaches is limited. In genome-wide association studies, hundreds of thousands single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) are genotyped for several hundreds of individuals. Usually, only a very smaller subset of these markers is associated with the trait. Existing methods for exact computation of standard test statistics are mostly based on a fixed-SNP-effect mixed linear model (MLM) and single marker analysis, for example, efficient mixed model analysis (EMMA). These methods require Bonferroni correction for multiple tests, which often is too conservative when the number of markers is vast. To address this concern, several approaches have been proposed in previous studies.

The ridge regression (Hoerl & Kennard 1970), stochastic search variable selection (George & McCulloch 1993; Yi *et al.* 2003), Bayesian shrinkage estimation (Meuwissen *et al.* 2001; Wang *et al.* 2005), penalized maximum likelihood (Zhang & Xu 2005; Hoggart *et al.* 2008; Zhang *et al.* 2012), empirical Bayes (Xu 2010) and Bayesian-LASSO (Bayesian-least absolute shrinkage and selection operator; Park & Casella 2008; Yi & Xu 2008) have been used to estimate the parameters in the oversaturated model. However, these methods are mainly proposed for linkage analysis in bi-parental segregation populations, rather than for GWAS in a natural population. GWAS has been used to separate the genetic foundation of quantitative traits (Zhang *et al.* 2005; Zhang *et al.* 2010; Yu *et al.* 2006; Kang *et al.* 2008; Zhou & Stephens 2012; Wang *et al.* 2016). The widely used approach, such as efficient mixed-model association (EMMA) (Kang *et al.* 2008; Zhou & Stephens

2012), was proposed for single marker analysis under the population structure and polygenic background controls. However, this method has relatively low power in detecting small-effect QTLs.

Multi-locus model approaches have been suggested to overcome these problems (Fridley *et al.* 2010; Lü *et al.* 2011). For example, a Bayesian-inspired penalized maximum likelihood approach (Zhang & Xu 2005; Hoggart *et al.* 2008) and PUMA (Penalized Unified Multiple-locus Association) (Hoffman *et al.* 2013). These methods can be used if the number of variables in the multi-locus model is not too large. Recent strategies for high dimensional modeling have focused on reducing the dimension of a large matrix and then selecting the most potentially associated SNPs by using shrinkage methods such as the LASSO and SCAD (smoothly clipped absolute deviation) penalty (Fan & Lv 2008; Wu *et al.* 2009). Although other multi-locus approaches have also been proposed by Segura *et al.* (2012), Moser *et al.* (2015), Liu *et al.* (2016), Wang *et al.* (2016) and Wen *et al.* (2017), further refinement and studies are still needed.

Several methods have been proposed in our lab, the knowledge about how to select these approaches is limited. In this study, we evaluated five multi-locus GWAS methods (pLARmEB, pKWmEB, mrMLM, FASTmrEMMA and ISIS EM-BLASSO) in our lab and one single-locus GWAS method (GEMMA) using five flowering time-related traits (LN10, LN16, LN22, FW and DW) in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and five quantitative traits (LR, LH, FWR, DWR and BS) in soybean.

Materials and Methods

The Arabidopsis thaliana datasets

The well-known *Arabidopsis thaliana* datasets with 199 accessions each with 216130 SNPs (Atwell *et al.* 2010) were downloaded from <http://www.arabidopsis.usc.edu/> and re-analyzed in this study. Five quantitative traits analyzed were LN10, LN16, and LN22 (leaf number at a flowering time at 10 °C, 16 °C, and 22 °C, respectively), fresh and dry weights (FW and DW). For the five traits, missing individuals in the genotype and phenotype datasets were deleted respectively. Also, the SNPs with minor allele frequency <5% were deleted respectively. Thus, the SNPs for LN10, LN16, LN22, FW, and DW were 206295, 206203, 206322, 207702 and 207702, respectively. The phenotypes of lines for the above five traits were 177, 176, 176, 95 and 95, respectively. The STRUCTURE software version 1.0 under Linux system (<http://web.stanford.edu/group/pritchardlab/structure.html>) was used to calculate population structure.

The Soybean datasets

Using all the 286 soybean cultivars obtained by stratified random sampling, from 6 geographic eco-types in China. Planted in three-row plots using a completely randomized design were evaluated at Jiangpu experimental station at Nanjing Agricultural University in 2014 and 2015. The plots were 1.5m wide and 2m

long. The seeds were used to conduct plastic container experiments. Approximately 0.3g of fresh leaves obtained from each cultivar in 2012 was used to extract genomic DNA by using the CATB (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide) as described by (Doyle *et al.* 1987). Tolerance was evaluated on five traits: length of main root (LR), the fresh and dry weights of roots (FWR and FDR), the biomass of seedlings (BS) and the length of hypocotyls (LH) of healthy seedlings after water solution treatments for approximately one week under greenhouse conditions. For the five traits, missing individuals in the genotype and phenotype datasets were deleted respectively. Also, the SNPs with minor allele frequency <5% were deleted respectively. The STRUCTURE software version 2.2 under Windows system (<http://web.stanford.edu/group/pritchardlab/structure.html>) was used to calculate population structure.

Methodologies for genomic-wide association studies

In this study, five multi-locus GWAS methods: pLARmEB (Zhang *et al.* 2017), pKWmEB (Ren *et al.* 2016), mrMLM (Wang *et al.* 2016), FASTmrEMMA (Wen *et al.* 2017) and ISIS EM-BLASSO (Tamba *et al.* 2017) in our lab and one single-locus GWAS method (GEMMA) were used to analyze five traits (LN10, LN16, LN22, FW and DW) in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and five traits (LR, LH, FWR, DWR and BS) in soybean.

mrMLM (multi-locus random-SNP-effect mixed linear model)

In the mrMLM (Wang *et al.* 2016), the single marker random effect linear mixed model (rMLM) method is an initial screening step for all markers that have *p* values smaller than 0.01. A consecutive number of markers passing the 0.01 threshold around an already selected marker (± 20 kb for real data analysis and ± 1 kb for simulated data analysis) are eliminated to reduce collinearity among selected markers. Only these selected markers are included in the multi-locus model for further evaluation, including estimation of marker effects and significance tests. Due to the shrinkage, the majority of markers are eliminated in the initial screening. Therefore, a smaller number of markers are left in the second stage analysis. This small number of surviving markers are then included in a multi-locus genetic model.

pLARmEB (polygene-background control-based least angle regression plus empirical Bayes)

In pLARmEB (Zhang *et al.* 2017), the least angle regression (LARS) algorithm is integrated with empirical Bayes to perform multi-locus GWAS for complex traits. To control polygenic background, the model transformation of Wen *et al.* (2017) is adopted. The LARS algorithm is then implemented on the transformed model to select SNPs that are most potentially associated with the trait; empirical Bayes is used to estimate the effects of all the selected SNPs and all the nonzero effects are further identified by likelihood ratio test so as to confirm true quantitative trait nucleotides (QTNs).

pKWmEB (Integration of Kruskal-Wallis test with empirical Bayes)

An integrated non-parametric method for multi-locus GWAS was proposed by [Ren et al. \(2016\)](#). First, a new model transformation of [Wen et al. \(2017\)](#) is used to control polygenic background. Using the modified model, the Kruskal-Wallis test is then used to scan each marker on the genome, with the purpose of selecting all the markers that were potentially associated with the trait. Finally, all the selected markers are placed into the multi-locus genetic model, empirical Bayes was used to estimate these effects, and a likelihood ratio test was used to identify all the nonzero effects. This called pKWmEB ([Ren 2016](#)).

FASTmrEMMA (fast multi-locus random-SNP-effect EMMA)

FASTmrEMMA is a multi-locus two-stage GWAS approach. FASTmrEMMA was proposed by [Wen et al. \(2017\)](#). In the first stage, SNP effect is treated as random and minor part of SNPs are picked up based on the prior premise that most SNPs should have no effect on the quantitative traits. Three techniques are implemented to save running time. First, a new matrix transformation is used to multiply original MLM, and its purpose is to whiten the covariance matrix of the polygenic matrix K and environmental noise. Then, a polygenic-to-residual variance ratio under the null hypothesis is fixed in all the single marker genome tests. Finally, the number of nonzero eigenvalues is specified as one. In the second stage, all the selected SNP effects in the first stage are placed into one multi-locus genetic model and then estimated by expectation and maximization empirical Bayes for true QTN identification.

ISIS EM-BLASSO (Iterative sure independence screening Expectation-Maximization Bayesian least absolute shrinkage and selection operator)

ISIS EM-BLASSO was proposed by [Tamba et al. \(2017\)](#). This approach first reduces the number of variables via correlation learning approach. In the screening stage, the number of SNPs is first reduced by selecting only SNPs that are significantly correlated with the response. SCAD method is applied, and relevant variables are selected while shrinking others to zero. In the next stage, significant predictors are found that are marginally uncorrelated with a response. Using an iterative modified sure independence screening procedure, the SIS procedure is repeated conditional on the previously selected variables to capture essential variables that are marginally uncorrelated with a response. This approach is extended by applying EM-Bayesian LASSO algorithm in the final stage. Parametric estimation and significance tests of variables are performed at this last stage.

The above five methods were implemented by R software mrMLM, which could be downloaded from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/mrMLM/index.html>.

GEMMA (genome-wide efficient mixed-model association)

GEMMA is an existing method ([Zhou et al. 2012](#)) for GWAS and used as a gold standard for comparison. This procedure is the fixed model version of the original MLM, in which β_i was treated as a fixed effect. The

method was implemented in the C software GEMMA (Zhou *et al.* 2012) (<http://www.xzlab.org/software.html>). The threshold of P-value was set as $0.05/p$ after Bonferroni correction for multiple tests, where p is the number of markers.

Results

Detection of significantly associated SNPs in *Arabidopsis thaliana*

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for LN10. As a result, 2 SNPs were found to be associated with LN10. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 4, and their heritabilities were 2.15 and 4.84, with the average of 3.5. For pLARmEB, 12 SNPs were found to be associated with LN10. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and their heritabilities were between 0.01 and 0.58, with the average of 0.14. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 3 SNPs were found to be associated with LN10. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 1, 4, and their heritabilities were between 0.49 and 1.15, with the average of 0.75. For pKWmEB, 1 SNPs was found to be associated with LN10. This SNP was located on chromosomes 5 and with heritability of 2.59. Across these methods, 17 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 1 SNPs was common (See Tables 1, 6, Table S1 and Figure 1 for details of the SNPS).

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for LN16. As a result, 2 SNPs was found to be associated with LN16. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 2, 5 and their heritabilities were 2.13 and 3.12, with the average of 2.62. For pLARmEB, 8 SNPs were found to be associated with LN16. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 1, 2, 4, 5 and their heritabilities were between 0.12 and 0.76, with the average of 0.66. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 4 SNPs were found to be associated with LN16. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 1, 3, 4, 5 and their heritabilities were between 0.23 and 2.11, with the average of 0.90. For pKWmEB, 2 SNPs was found to be associated with LN16. These SNPs was located on chromosomes 1, 2 and with heritabilities of 1.59 and 2.52, with the average of 2.06. For FASTmrEMMA, 1 SNPs was found to be associated with LN16. This SNP was located on chromosomes 3 and with heritability of 3.97. Across these methods, 15 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 2 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for LN22. As a result, 3 SNPs was found to be associated with LN22. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 1, 5 and their heritabilities were between 2.68 and 3.09, with the average of 2.95. For pLARmEB, 6 SNPs were found to be associated with LN22. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 1, 3, 5 and their heritabilities were between 0.04 and 1.81, with the average of 0.74 For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 6 SNPs were found to be associated with LN22. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 1, 3, 5 and their heritabilities were between 0.52 and 1.94, with the average of 1.57. For pKWmEB, 2 SNPs was found to be associated with LN22. These SNPs was located on chromosomes 1, 5 and with heritabilities of 2.08 and 5.25, with the average of 3.67. For FASTmrEMMA, 1 SNPs was found to be associated with LN22.

This SNP was located on chromosomes 5 and with heritability of 2.14. Across these methods, 13 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 3 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for FW. As a result, 2 SNPs were found to be associated with FW. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 2, 3 and their heritabilities were 11.19 and 6.40, with the average of 8.79. For pLARmEB, 1 SNP was found to be associated with FW. This SNP was located on chromosomes 1 and with heritability of 0.63. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 3 SNPs were found to be associated with FW. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 2, 4 and their heritabilities were between 6.01E-08 and 6.31, with the average of 2.46. For pKWmEB, 2 SNPs were found to be associated with FW. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 5 and with heritabilities of 1.97 and 3.51, with the average of 2.74. For FASTmrEMMA, 2 SNPs were found to be associated with FW. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 2, 3 and with heritabilities of 3.36 and 6.44, with the average of 4.90. Across these methods, 8 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 1 SNP was common.

pLARmEB was used to detect SNPs for DW. As a result, 4 SNPs were found to be associated with DW. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 1, 3, 4 and their heritabilities were between 0.01 and 2.60, with the average of 1.09. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 4 SNPs were found to be associated with DW. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 2, 4, 5 and their heritabilities were between 2.84 and 4.71, with the average of 3.88. For FASTmrEMMA, 1 SNP was found to be associated with DW. This SNP was located on chromosomes 2 and with heritability of 7.63. Across these methods, 8 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 1 SNP was common (Tables 1, 2 and Table S1, Figure 1).

In summary, sixty-one SNPs were found to be associated with the five traits, and only eight SNPs were common across these methods.

Detection of significantly associated SNPs in Soybean with the water treatment in 2014

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for LR. As a result, 13 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were between 0 and 0.14. For pLARmEB, 16 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were between 0.7 and 9.6. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 17 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were between 1.07 and 7.03. For pKWmEB, 3 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities between 2.78 and 5.4. For FASTmrEMMA, 8 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities between 0.013 and 0.043. Across these methods, 57 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 33 SNPs were common (Tables 2, Table S2 and Figure 2).

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for LH. As a result, 6 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were between 0.046 and 0.067. For pLARmEB, 5 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were between 2.97 and 5.86. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 11 SNPs were found to be

associated with LH and their heritabilities were between 1.39 and 5.25. For pKWmEB, 3 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities between 2.48 and 7.31. For FASTmrEMMA, 5 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities between 0.019 and 0.039. For GEMMA, 1 SNPs was found to be associated with LH and its heritability was 0.013. Across these methods, 31 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 13 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for FWR. As a result, 7 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities were between 0.037 and 0.079. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 17 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities were between 0.96 and 6.84. For pKWmEB, 8 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities between 1.89E-04 and 5.93. For FASTmrEMMA, 6 SNPs were found to be associated with and their heritabilities between 0.037 and 0.079. Across these methods, 38 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 11 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for DWR. As a result, 2 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities were 0.09 and 0.10. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 15 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities between 0.0004 and 3.85. For pKWmEB, 2 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities were 0.27 and 0.005. For FASTmrEMMA, 8 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities between 0.007 and 0.05. Across these methods, 27 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 6 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for BS. As a result, 14 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities were between 0.02 and 0.11. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 23 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between 0 and 9.48. For pKWmEB, 9 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between 1.00E-04 and 6.78. For FASTmrEMMA, 9 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between 0.014 and 0.06. Across these methods, 55 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 17 SNPs were common (Tables 2, Table S2 and Figure 2).

In summary, 209 SNPs were found to be associated with the five traits, and only 80 SNPs were common across these methods.

Detection of significantly associated SNPs in Soybean with the water treatment in 2015

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for LR. As a result, 9 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were between 0.03 and 0.12. For pLARmEB, 10 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were between 1.33 and 9.68. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 16 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were between 0.74 and 9.68. For pKWmEB, 5 SNPs were found to be

associated with LR and their heritabilities between 2.47 and 8.43. For FASTmrEMMA, 5 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities between 0.014 and 0.043. For GEMMA, 2 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were 0.011 and 0.016. Across these methods, 47 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 37 SNPs were common (Tables 3, Table S3 and Figure 3).

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for LH. As a result, 6 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were between 0.04 and 0.18. For pLARM EB, 9 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were between 0.02 and 5.35. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 12 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were between 0.73 and 10.37. For pKWmEB, 3 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities between 1.46 and 5.36. For FASTmrEMMA, 6 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities between 0.015 and 0.031, with the average of 0.027. Across these methods, 36 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 18 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for FWR. As a result, 10 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities were between 0.04 and 0.104. For pLARM EB, 13 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities were between 0 and 5.34. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 12 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities were between 0 and 4.7. For pKWmEB, 6 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities between 2.2 and 6.10. For FASTmrEMMA, 5 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities between 0.027 and 0.041. Across these methods, 46 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 12 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for DWR. As a result, 10 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities were 0.04 and 0.104. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 16 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities between 0.08 and 4.23. For pKWmEB, 4 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities between $1.54E-06$ and 9.18. For FASTmrEMMA, 4 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities between 0.027 and 0.041. Across these methods, 34 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and none of the SNPs was common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for BS. As a result, 10 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities were between 0.04 and 0.104. For pLARM EB, 45 SNPs were found to be associated with and their heritabilities were between 0.01 and 9.68. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 19 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between 0.48 and 5.6. For pKWmEB, 4 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between $1.54E-06$ and 9.18. For FASTmrEMMA, 7 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between 0.011 and 0.05. Across these methods, 85 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 12 SNPs were common (Tables 3, Table S3 and Figure 3).

In summary, 251 SNPs were found to be associated with the five traits, and only Seventy-nine SNPs were common across these methods.

Detection of significantly associated SNPs in Soybean with the salt treatment in 2014

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for LR. As a result, 5 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were between 0.07 and 0.11. For pLARmEB, 9 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were between 1.37 and 5.3. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 13 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were between 1.4 and 5.68. For pKWmEB, 7 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities between $3.76E-08$ and 4.9. For FASTmrEMMA, 2 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities between 0.45 and 0.07. Across these methods, 36 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 18 SNPs were common (Tables 4, Table S4 and Figure 4).

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for LH. As a result, 6 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were between 0.04 and 0.11. For pLARmEB, 7 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were between $4.18E-05$ and 4.01. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 17 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were between $1.58E-08$ and 7.43. For pKWmEB, 2 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were 3.98 and 4.35. For FASTmrEMMA, 7 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities between 0.02 and 0.04. Across these methods, 39 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 12 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for FWR. As a result, 8 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities were between 0.04 and 0.14. For pLARmEB, 85 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities were between 0.02 and 3.1. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 9 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities were between 0.64 and 9.78. For pKWmEB, 2 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities were 1.66 and 3.21. For FASTmrEMMA, 6 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities between 0.01 and 0.08. Across these methods, 110 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 13 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for DWR. As a result, 3 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities were 0.05 and 0.12. For pLARmEB, 1 SNP were found to be associated with DWR and its heritability was 0.135. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 18 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities between 0.007 and 6.43, with the average of 1.91. For pKWmEB, 1 SNP was found to be associated with DWR with heritability of 0.196. For FASTmrEMMA, 6 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities between 0.01 and 0.03. For GEMMA, 1 SNP was found to be associated

with DWR with heritability of 0.011. Across these methods, 30 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 6 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for BS. As a result, 15 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities were between 0.02 and 0.18. For pLARmEB, 40 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities were between 0.04 and 8.51. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 19 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between 0.49 and 11.16. For pKWmEB, 11 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between 1.14 and 5.46. For FASTmrEMMA, 10 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between 0.01 and 0.03. For GEMMA, 1 SNP was found to be associated with BS with heritability of 0.013. Across these methods, 96 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 33 SNPs were common (Tables 4, Table S4 and Figure 4).

In summary, 311 SNPs were found to be associated with the five traits, and only Eighty-two SNPs were common across these methods.

Detection of significantly associated SNPs in Soybean with the salt treatment in 2015

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for LR. As a result, 7 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were between 0.033 and 0.16. For pLARmEB, 8 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were between 2.90E-05 and 5.29. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 9 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities were between 1.54 and 9.49. For pKWmEB, 1 SNP was found to be associated with LR with heritability of 6.50E-08. For FASTmrEMMA, 4 SNPs were found to be associated with LR and their heritabilities between 0.01 and 0.03. Across these methods, 23 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 11 SNPs were common (Tables 5, Table S5 and Figure 5).

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for LH. As a result, 5 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were between 0.02 and 0.16. For pLARmEB, 5 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were between 0.0002 and 12.73. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 14 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were between 0.91 and 9.82. For pKWmEB, 5 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities were 2.47 and 4.88. For FASTmrEMMA, 7 SNPs were found to be associated with LH and their heritabilities between 0.016 and 0.045. Across these methods, 42 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 22 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for FWR. As a result, 7 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities were between 0.03 and 0.09. For pLARmEB, 35 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities were between 0.01 and 6.23. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 16 SNPs were found to be

associated with FWR and their heritabilities were between 0.61 and 7.18. For pKWmEB, 9 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities were 7.83E-05 and 8.16. For FASTmrEMMA, 5 SNPs were found to be associated with FWR and their heritabilities between 0.02 and 0.03. Across these methods, 113 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 55 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for DWR. As a result, 6 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities were 0.01 and 0.16. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 23 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities between 0.004 and 7.41. For pKWmEB, 65 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities between 1.00E-04 and 2.15. For FASTmrEMMA, 3 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities between 0.02 and 0.06. For GEMMA, 63 SNPs were found to be associated with DWR and their heritabilities between 0.011 and 0.058. Across these methods, 160 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 11 SNPs were common.

mrMLM was used to detect SNPs for BS. As a result, 18 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities were between 0.02 and 0.16. For pLARmEB, 39 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities were between 0.02 and 4.58. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 19 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between 7.69E-06 and 3.72. For pKWmEB, 8 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between 0.197 and 4.67. For FASTmrEMMA, 12 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between 0.0083 and 0.046. For GEMMA, 14 SNPs were found to be associated with BS and their heritabilities between 0.011 and 0.017. Across these methods, 91 SNPs were found to be associated with the trait and only 8 SNPs were common (Tables 5, Table S5 and Figure 5).

In summary, 407 SNPs were found to be associated with the five traits, and only 107 SNPs were common across these methods.

Previously reported genes around the above significantly associated SNPs

Arabidopsis thaliana datasets

With mrMLM, 2 previously reported genes (*NGA2* and *FRI*) by Alvarez *et al.* (2006) and Lee *et al.* (1993) were found to be around the two SNPs associated with LN10. The two genes were located on chromosomes 3 and 4, respectively. For pLARmEB, 14 previously reported genes (*BRN2*, *ACLA-1*, *ARF6*, *UFO*, *SUF4*, *HTA8*, *IPP2*, *HULK3*, *NGATHA4*, *PGI1*, *TAR2*, *FD*, *FLC*, *ATGA20OX2*) by (Kim, *et al.* 2013; Fatland *et al.* 2005; Nagpal *et al.* 2005; Schmid *et al.* 2005; Bao *et al.* 2011; Choi *et al.* 2007; Phillips *et al.* 2008; Jali *et al.* 2014; Alvarez *et al.* 2016; Yu *et al.* 2000; Stepanova *et al.* 2008; Abe *et al.* 2005; Edwards *et al.* 2006; Rieu *et al.* 2007) were found to be associated with LN10. These genes were located on chromosomes 1, 2, 3, 4, 5. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 4 previously reported genes (*CRY2*, *RPL27AB*, *PGI1*, *TAR2*) by (Endo *et al.* 2007;

Szakonyi *et al.* 2011; Yu *et al.* 2000; Stepanova *et al.* 2008) were found to be associated with LN10. These genes were located on chromosomes 1, 4. For pKWmEB, 1 previously reported gene (*APRF1*) by Kapolas *et al.* (2016) was found to be associated with LN10. This gene was located on chromosomes 5. Across these methods, 19 previously reported genes were found to be associated with the trait and only 2 genes were common. (See Table 6 for genes details).

With mrMLM 3 previously reported genes (*SPL3, FES1, BOA*) by (Cardon *et al.* 1997; Ding *et al.* 2013; Dai *et al.* 2011) were found to be associated with LN16. These genes were located on chromosomes 2, 5 and their heritabilities were 2.13 and 3.12, with the average of 2.62. For pLARmEB, 11 previously reported genes (*ARF6, FT, SPL3, FES1, FRI, ATGA20OX3, FLC, CORYNE, CO, COL1*) by (Nagpal *et al.* 2005; Xu *et al.* 2010; Cardon *et al.* 1997; Ding *et al.* 2013; Lee *et al.* 1993; Ascencio-Ibanez *et al.* 2005; Phillips *et al.* 1995; Levy *et al.* 2002; Casamitjana *et al.* 2003; Suarez-Lopez *et al.* 2001; Osterberg *et al.* 2002) were found to be associated with LN16. These genes were located on chromosomes 1, 2, 4, 5 and their heritabilities were between 0.12 and 0.76, with the average of 0.66. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 4 previously reported genes (*SUF4, MNP, MED25, ATP14K3*) by (Kim *et al.* 2006; Zhao *et al.* 2004; Iñigo *et al.* 2012; Akhter *et al.* 2015) were found to be associated with LN16. These genes were located on chromosomes 1, 3, 4, 5 and their heritabilities were between 0.23 and 2.11, with the average of 0.90. For pKWmEB, 2 previously reported genes (*RPL27AB, CKA4*) by (Szakonyi *et al.* 2011; Wang *et al.* 2016) were found to be associated with LN16. These genes were located on chromosomes 1, 2 and with heritabilities of 1.59 and 2.52, with the average of 2.06. For FASTmrEMMA, 1 previously reported gene (*MNP*) by Zhao *et al.* 2004 was found to be associated with LN16. This gene was located on chromosomes 3 and with heritability of 3.97. Across these methods, 17 genes were found to be associated with the trait and only 3 genes were common.

With mrMLM 3 previously reported genes (*TIL1, HTA9, GAS41*) by (Del Olmo *et al.* 2009; Choi *et al.* 2007; Zacharaki *et al.* 2012) were found to be associated with LN22. These genes were located on chromosomes 1, 5 and their heritabilities were between 2.68 and 3.09, with the average of 2.95. For pLARmEB, 7 previously reported genes (*UFO, SUF4, SPL4, SPL5, NGA2, STE14A, GAS41*) by (Durfee *et al.* 2003; Kim *et al.* 2006; Jung *et al.* 2006; Jung *et al.* 2006; Alvarez *et al.* 2016; Schmid *et al.* 2005; Bracha-Drori *et al.* 2008; Zacharaki *et al.* 2012) were found to be associated with LN22. These genes were located on chromosomes 1, 3, 5 and their heritabilities were between 0.04 and 1.81, with the average of 0.74. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 8 previously reported genes (*TIL1, UFO, SUF4, HTA9, NAC066, NGA2, SAF1, GAS41*) by (Del Olmo *et al.* 2009; Durfee *et al.* 2003; Kim *et al.* 2006; Choi *et al.* 2007; Mitsuda *et al.* 2005; Alvarez *et al.* 2006; Kim *et al.* 2011; Zacharaki *et al.* 2012) were found to be associated with LN22. These genes were located on chromosomes 1, 3, 5 and their heritabilities were between 0.52 and 1.94, with the average of 1.57. For pKWmEB, 2 previously reported genes (*GAMMA CA2, FLC*) by (Fernando *et al.* 2009; Levy *et al.* 2002) were found to be associated with LN22. These genes were located on chromosomes 1, 5 and with heritabilities of 2.08 and 5.25, with the average of 3.67. For FASTmrEMMA, 1 previously reported gene (*GAS41*) by Zacharaki *et al.* (2012) was

found to be associated with LN22. This gene was located on chromosomes 5 and with heritability of 2.14. Across these methods, 14 genes were found to be associated with the trait and only 5 genes were common.

With mrMLM 2 previously reported genes (*AGL44*, *ATCHR12*) by (Zhang *et al.* 1998; Mlynárová *et al.* 2007) were found to be associated with FW. These SNPs were located on chromosomes 2, 3 and their heritabilities were 11.19 and 6.40, with the average of 8.79. For pLARmEB, 2 previously reported genes (*5PTASE13*, *BT3*) by (Ananieva *et al.* 2008; Du *et al.* 2004) were found to be associated with FW. These genes were located on chromosomes 1 and with heritability of 0.63. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 3 previously reported genes (*AGL44*, *GALT2*, *CSDP1*) by (Zhang *et al.* 1998; Basu *et al.* (2015); Kim *et al.* 2006) were found to be associated with FW. These genes were located on chromosomes 2, 4 and their heritabilities were between 6.01E-08 and 6.31, with the average of 2.46. For pKWmEB, 2 previously reported genes (*BUD2*, *THAS1*) by (Ge *et al.* 2006; Field *et al.* 2008) were found to be associated with FW. These genes were located on chromosomes 5 and with heritabilities of 1.97 and 3.51, with the average of 2.74. For FASTmrEMMA, 2 previously reported genes (*AGL44*, *WOX11*) by (Zhang *et al.* 1998; Liu *et al.* 2014) were found to be associated with FW. These genes were located on chromosomes 2, 3 and with heritabilities of 3.36 and 6.44, with the average of 4.90. Across these methods, 9 genes were found to be associated with the trait and only 1 gene was common.

With pLARmEB 3 previously reported genes (*SGF29a*, *CPK32*, *PLAT1*) by (Kaldis *et al.* 2010; Choi *et al.* 2005; Hyun *et al.* 2014) were found to be associated with DW. These genes were located on chromosomes 1, 3, 4 and their heritabilities were between 0.01 and 2.60, with the average of 1.09. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 4 previously reported genes (*AGL44*, *CTU2*, *BUD2*, *SEF*) by (Zhang *et al.* 1998; Philipp *et al.* 2014; Ge *et al.* 2006; Choi *et al.* 2007) were found to be associated with DW. These genes were located on chromosomes 2, 4, 5 and their heritabilities were between 2.84 and 4.71, with the average of 3.88. For FASTmrEMMA, 1 previously reported gene (*AGL44*) by Zhang *et al.* (1998) was found to be associated with DW. This gene was located on chromosomes 2 and with heritability of 7.63. Across these methods, 7 genes were found to be associated with the trait and only 1 SNP was common (Table 6).

In summary, 66 genes were found to be associated with the five traits, and only 12 genes were common across these methods (Table 6).

Soybean datasets with salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014 and 2015

With pLARmEB, 1 previously reported gene (*Glyma.02g067700*) by (Phang *et al.* 2008) was found to be associated with LR. This gene was located on chromosome 2. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 6 previously reported genes (*Glyma.13g162900*, *Glyma.14g093900*, *Glyma17g052400*, *Glyma.17g052500*, *Glyma.17g047300*, *Glyma.18g023000*) by (Phang *et al.* 2008) were found to be associated with LR. These genes were located on

chromosomes 13, 14, 17, 18. Across these methods, 7 previously reported genes were found to be associated with the trait and none was common. (See Table 7 for genes details).

With pLARmEB, 1 previously reported gene (*Glyma.03g157800*) by (Ren *et al.* 2016) was found to be associated with LH. This gene was located on chromosome 3. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 2 previously reported genes (*Glyma.03g157800*, *Glyma.17g261700*) by (Ren *et al.* 2016) were found to be associated with LRH. These genes were located on chromosomes 3, 17. Across these methods, 2 previously reported genes were found to be associated with the trait and only 1 was common. (Table 7).

With mrMLM 2 previously reported genes (*Glyma.06g143800*, *Glyma.18g124700*) by (Liao *et al.* 2008) were found to be associated with FWR. These genes were located on chromosomes 6, 18. For pLARmEB, 15 previously reported genes (*Glyma.01g040000*, *Glyma.01g040200*, *Glyma.02g126100*, *Glyma.03g260200*, *Glyma.04g107500*, *Glyma.04g061500*, *Glyma.05g040700*, *Glyma.06g155500*, *Glyma.14g007700*, *Glyma.15g264000*, *Glyma.15g264400*, *Glyma.15g168200*, *Glyma.16g168400*, *Glyma.16g165900*, *Glyma.17g045300*) by (Zhu *et al.* 2016; Ji *et al.* 2010; Liao *et al.* 2008) were found to be associated with FWR. These genes were located on chromosomes 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 14, 15, 16, 17. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 4 previously reported genes (*Glyma.06g155200*, *Glyma.16g202200*, *Glyma.17g231900*, *Glyma.18g124700*) by (Liao *et al.* 2003) were found to be associated with FWR. These genes were located on chromosomes 6, 17, 18. For pKWmEB, 4 previously reported genes (*Glyma.02g121800*, *Glyma.17g231900*, *Glyma.18g124700*, *Glyma.18g046300*) by (Zhu *et al.* 2016; Liao *et al.* 2008) were found to be associated with FWR. These genes were located on chromosomes 2, 17, 18 and with heritabilities of 2.08 and 5.25, with the average of 3.67. For FASTmrEMMA, 1 previously reported gene (*Glyma.06g145300*) by Liao *et al.*(2008) was found to be associated with FWR. This gene was located on chromosomes 6. Across these methods, 26 genes were found to be associated with the trait and only 2 genes were common.

With mrMLM 9 previously reported genes (*Glyma.01g122800*, *Glyma.04g107900*, *Glyma.06g073200*, *Glyma.06g073100*, *Glyma.06g074300*, *Glyma.06g042100*, *Glyma.14g213600*, *Glyma.15g049000*, *Glyma.15g048600*) by (Zhu *et al.* 2016; Phang *et al.* 2008) were found to be associated with DWR. These genes were located on chromosomes 1, 4, 6, 14, 15. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 8 previously reported genes (*Glyma.02g236200*, *Glyma.02g121800*, *Glyma.03g260200*, *Glyma.05g192400*, *Glyma.14g204100*, *Glyma.14g084700*, *Glyma.15g172500*, *Glyma.18g124700*) by (Zhu *et al.* 2016; Phang *et al.* 2008) were found to be associated with DWR. These genes were located on chromosomes 2, 3, 5, 14, 15, 18. For pKWmEB, 6 previously reported genes (*Glyma.03g128200*, *Glyma.04g205400*, *Glyma.06g079800*, *Glyma.16g063200*, *Glyma.18g081200*, *Glyma.20g002000*) by (Zhu *et al.* 2016; Liao *et al.* 2008; Phang *et al.* 2008) were found to be associated with DWR. These genes were located on chromosomes 3, 4, 6. For GEMMA, 1 previously reported gene (*Glyma.04g142700*) by Zhu *et al.* (2016) was found to be associated with DWR. This gene was located on chromosomes 4. Across these methods, 24 genes were found to be associated with the trait and none was common.

With mrMLM 10 previously reported genes (*Glyma.02g131700*, *Glyma.14g213600*, *Glyma.14g194800*, *Glyma.15g049000*, *Glyma.15g048600*, *Glyma.15g172500*, *Glyma.17g167100*, *Glyma.18g040800*, *Glyma.18g071600*, *Glyma.20g223300*) were found to be associated with BS. These genes were located on chromosomes 2, 14, 15, 18. For pLARmEB, 6 previously reported genes (*Glyma.02g013100*, *Glyma.03g250600*, *Glyma.06g017900*, *Glyma.13g170000*, *Glyma.15g172500*, *Glyma.18g040800*) were found to be associated with BS. These genes were located on chromosomes 2, 3, 6, 13. For ISIS EM-BLASSO, 8 previously reported genes (*Glyma.02g131700*, *Glyma.02g253100*, *Glyma.05g122400*, *Glyma.05g197700*, *Glyma.14g194800*, *Glyma.17g239200*, *Glyma.18g071600*, *Glyma.20g223300*) were found to be associated with BS. These genes were located on chromosomes 2, 5, 14, 17, 18, 20. For pKWmEB, 1 previously reported genes (*Glyma.20g223300*) was found to be associated with BS. These genes were located on chromosome 20. For FASTmrEMMA, 6 previously reported genes, (*Glyma.02g240600*, *Glyma.05g122400*, *Glyma.14g204100*, *Glyma.18g040700*, *Glyma.18g040800*, *Glyma.18g071600*) were found to be associated with BS. These genes were located on chromosomes 2, 5, 14, 18. For GEMMA, 2 previously reported genes, (*Glyma.18g040800*, *Glyma.18g071600*) were found to be associated with BS. These genes were located on chromosomes 18, across these methods, 33 genes were found to be associated with the trait and only 7 genes were common. (Table 7).

In summary, 83 genes were found to be associated with the five traits, and only 10 genes were common across these methods (Table 7).

Discussion

GWAS refers to an approach that involves rapidly scanning markers across the complete sets of genomes, of many plants or animal to find genetic variations associated with a particular trait. GWAS methods are chiefly concerned with determining alleles associated with various SNPs in each study subject and making statistical comparisons to identify SNPs or genes associated with a particular trait. Usually, only a small subset of SNPs is associated with the phenotype of a trait. To address this issue, several multi-locus GWAS approaches have already been published in the literature (Zhou *et al.* 2013; Segura *et al.* 2012; Moser *et al.* 2015). When the size of the marker is not large, all marker effects and their interactions are included in a single model, such as the empirical Bayes method (Lü *et al.* 2011). If the marker number is large, this single model approach is not feasible. Zhou *et al.* (2013) developed a Bayesian sparse linear mixed model, and Moser *et al.* (2015) proposed a Bayesian mixture model. Comparison of GWAS methods with polygenic background control provides one simple and efficient way for multi-locus GWAS.

Across the traits, different methods detected the various number of SNPs. Using the *Arabidopsis Thaliana* datasets, at LN10 trait, pLARmEB (12 SNPs) is the best followed by ISIS EM-BLASSO (3 SNPs), it means pLARmEB is the best for this trait. At LN16 pLARmEB (8 SNPs) is the best followed by ISIS EM-BLASSO

(4 SNPs), meaning pLARmEB is the best for this trait. At LN22 pLARmEB (6 SNPs) and ISIS EM-BLASSO (6 SNPs) are both the best for this trait. ISIS EM-BLASSO (3 SNPs) emerged the best for the FW trait while pLARmEB (4 SNPs) was the best for DW trait. Clearly, pLARmEB detected the highest number of SNPs across the five traits as compared to the other five methods.

In the same way, with the soybean datasets with the water treatment in 2014, at LR trait, ISIS EM-BLASSO (17 SNPs) is the best followed by pLARmEB (16 SNPs), it means ISIS EM-BLASSO is the best for this trait. At LH, ISIS EM-BLASSO (11 SNPs) is the best followed by mrMLM (6 SNPs), meaning ISIS EM-BLASSO is the best for this trait. At FWR, DWR and BS ISIS EM-BLASSO emerged the best with (17 SNPs), (15 SNPs) and (23 SNPs) respectively. Clearly, ISIS EM-BLASSO detected the highest number of SNPs across the five traits as compared to the other five methods. Soybean datasets with water treatment in 2015, at LR trait, ISIS EM-BLASSO (16 SNPs) is the best followed by pLARmEB (10 SNPs), it means ISIS EM-BLASSO is the best for this trait. At LH, ISIS EM-BLASSO (12 SNPs) is the best followed by pLARmEB (9 SNPs), meaning ISIS EM-BLASSO is the best for this trait. At FWR pLARmEB (13 SNPs) is the best followed by ISIS EM-BLASSO (12), meaning pLARmEB is the best for this trait. At DWR, ISIS EM-BLASSO emerged the best with (17 SNPs) while at BS pLARmEB (45 SNPs) was the best. Clearly, pLARmEB detected the highest number of SNPs across the five traits as compared to the other five methods.

Similarly, with the Soybean datasets with salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014, at LR trait, ISIS EM-BLASSO (13 SNPs) is the best followed by pLARmEB (9 SNPs), it means ISIS EM-BLASSO is the best for this trait. At LH, ISIS EM-BLASSO (17 SNPs) is the best followed by FASTmrEMMA (7 SNPs), meaning ISIS EM-BLASSO is the best for this trait. At FWR, pLARmEB (85 SNPs) is the best followed by ISIS EM-BLASSO (9 SNPs). For DWR, ISIS EM-BLASSO (18 SNPs) is the best followed by FASTmrEMMA (6 SNPs), meaning ISIS EM-BLASSO is the best for this trait. At BS, pLARmEB emerged the best with (40 SNPs). Clearly, pLARmEB detected the highest number of SNPs across the five traits as compared to the other five methods. Soybean datasets with salt (NaCl) treatment in 2015, at LR trait, ISIS EM-BLASSO (9 SNPs) is the best followed by pLARmEB (8 SNPs), it means ISIS EM-BLASSO is the best for this trait. At LH, ISIS EM-BLASSO (14 SNPs) is the best followed by FASTmrEMMA (7 SNPs), meaning ISIS EM-BLASSO is the best for this trait. At FWR pLARmEB (35 SNPs) is the best followed by ISIS EM-BLASSO (16), meaning pLARmEB is the best for this trait. At DWR, pKWmEB emerged the best with (65 SNPs) while at BS pLARmEB (39 SNPs) was the best. Clearly, pLARmEB detected the highest number of SNPs across the five traits as compared to the other five methods. We, therefore, recommend the joint implementation of several methods in the GWAS analyses of one trait. Our results are similar to the previous studies by [Zhang et al. \(2017\)](#).

Although pLARmEB, FASTmrEMMA, and mrMLM had similar powers of QTN detection in the analysis, a different number of genes were detected in real data analysis. For the *Arabidopsis* datasets; pLARmEB with 14 previously reported genes was the best method for the LN10 trait. For LN16 trait, pLARmEB with 11 previously reported genes emerged the best while, for L22, FW, and DW, ISIS EM-BLASSO method was the best with 8, 3 and 4 previously reported genes respectively, (Table 6). The pLARmEB method identified more known genes than the other five methods, indicating that this multi-locus model (pLARmEB) has a higher power for QTN detection than the other multi-locus model (ISIS EM-BLASSO, mrMLM, pKWmEB, FASTmrEMMA) and the single multi-locus method (GEMMA). Using Soybean datasets in 2014 and 2015; ISIS EM-BLASSO with 6 previously reported genes was the best method for the LR trait. For LH trait, ISIS EM-BLASSO with 2 previously reported genes emerged the best while, for FWR, pLARmEB with 14 previously reported genes emerged the best. For DWR, and BS, mrMLM method was the best with 10 and 9 previously reported genes respectively, (Table 7). The mrMLM method identified more known genes than the other five methods, indicating that this multi-locus model (mrMLM) has a higher power for QTN detection than the other multi-locus model (ISIS EM-BLASSO, pLARmEB, pKWmEB, FASTmrEMMA) and the single multi-locus method (GEMMA). Our results are similar to the previous studies by [Zhang et al. \(2017\)](#).

In summary, the GWAS approaches were able to detect approximately 10 to 20% common genes and SNPs in the *Arabidopsis Thaliana* datasets, and about 12 to 35% common genes and SNPs in soybean datasets in 2014 and 2015; it means they are complementary in nature.

Conclusion

We evaluated five multi-locus methods (pLARmEB, pKWmEB, mrMLM, FASTmrEMMA and ISIS EM-BLASSO) and one single-locus method (GEMMA) using five traits (LN10, LN16, LN22, FW and DW) in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. As a result, 482 SNPs were found to be associated with the above five traits. Among these SNPs detected, sixty-seven (13.9%) SNPs were common across six methods. Around these significantly associated SNPs, sixty-six genes had been confirmed by biological experiments to be responsive for the above five traits. Among these previously reported genes, twelve (18.2%) were common across the five methods, and no previously reported gene was identified by GEMMA. Approximately 10 to 20 % SNPs or genes were common. This means that most GWAS methods complement each other. GEMMA did not detect any genes, although it runs the fastest. Similarly, we evaluated the five multi-locus methods and one single-locus method above using five quantitative traits (LR, LH, FWR, DWR and BS) in Soybean datasets in 2014 and 2015. With water treatment in 2014 and 2015, 460 SNPs were found to be associated with the above five traits. Among these SNPs detected, 159 (34.57%) SNPs were common across various methods. Approximately 35% SNPs were common. The soybean datasets with salt (NaCl) treatment 2014 and 2015; 718 SNPs were found to be associated with the above five traits. Among these SNPs detected, 189 (26.32%) SNPs were common across six methods. Around these significantly associated SNPs, eighty-three genes had been confirmed by biological

experiments to be responsive for the above five traits. Among these previously reported genes, ten (12.05%) were common across the five methods. Approximately 12 to 30 % SNPs or genes were common. This means that most GWAS methods complement each other. This study adds new information that most of GWAS approaches are complementary in nature.

Author Contributions

Conceived and designed the experiments: YMZ. Performed the experiments: JYF YLN XLY YMZ. Analyzed the data: MMO YMZ. Wrote the paper: MMO YMZ.

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Table 1. Significantly associated SNPs Block for 5 traits in *Arabidopsis Thaliana* using six GWAS methods

Trait	FASTmrEMMA	ISIS EM-BLASSO	mrMLM	pKWmEB	pLARmEB	GEMMA
LN10	10	27	23	9	77	0
LN16	16	25	18	23	49	0
LN22	13	23	22	20	36	2
FW	7	15	8	11	13	0
DW	6	12	1	4	13	0

LN10, LN16, LN22: leaf number at a flowering time at 10 0C, 16 0C, and 22 0C, respectively. FW: fresh weight; DW: dry weight

Table 2. Significantly associated SNPs Block for 5 Traits, *Soybean in 2014* with the water treatment using six GWAS methods

Trait	FASTmrEMMA	ISIS EM-BLASSO	mrMLM	pKWmEB	pLARmEB	GEMMA
LR	8	17	13	3	16	0
LH	5	11	6	3	5	1
FWR	6	17	7	8	0	
DWR	8	15	2	2	0	0
BS	9	23	14	9	0	0

LR: main root length; LH: length of hypocotyls of healthy seedlings after treatments with control; FWR: the fresh weights of roots; DWR: dry weights of roots; BS: the biomass of seedlings.

Table 3. Significantly associated SNPs Block for 5 traits, *Soybean in 2015* with the water treatment using six GWAS methods

Trait	FASTmrEMMA	ISIS EM-BLASSO	mrMLM	pKWmEB	pLARmEB	GEMMA
LR	5	16	9	5	10	2
LH	6	12	6	3	9	0
FWR	5	12	10	6	13	0
DWR	4	16	10	4	0	0
BS	7	19	10	4	45	0

LR: main root length; LH: length of hypocotyls of healthy seedlings after treatments with control; FWR: the fresh weights of roots; DWR: dry weights of roots; BS: the biomass of seedlings.

Figure 1. Manhattant and QQ plots for significantly associated SNPs Block for 5 traits in *Arabidopsis Thaliana* using mrMLM GWAS method

Figure 2. Manhattan and QQ plots for significantly associated SNPs Block for 5 Traits, *Soybean* with the water treatment in 2014 using mrMLM GWAS method

Figure 3. Manhatt and QQ plots for significantly associated SNPs Block for five Traits, *Soybean* with the water treatment in 2015 using mrMLM GWAS method

Figure 4. Manhattan and QQ plots significantly associated SNPs Block for five Traits *Soybean* with the salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014 using mrMLM GWAS method

Figure 5. Manhattan and QQ plots for significantly associated SNPs Block for five Traits, *Soybean* with salt (NaCl) treatment in 2015 using mrMLM GWAS method

Table 4. Significantly associated SNPs Block for 5 traits, *Soybean in 2014* with the salt (NaCl) treatment using six GWAS methods

Trait	FASTmrEMMA	ISIS EM-BLASSO	mrMLM	pKWmEB	pLARmEB	GEMMA
LR	2	13	5	7	9	0
LH	7	17	6	2	7	0
FWR	6	9	8	2	85	0
DWR	6	18	3	1	1	1
BS	10	19	15	11	40	1

LR: main root length; LH: length of hypocotyls of healthy seedlings after treatments with control; FWR: the fresh weights of roots; DWR: dry weights of roots; BS: the biomass of seedlings.

Table 5. Significantly associated SNPs Block for 5 Traits, *Soybean in 2015* with the salt (NaCl) treatment using six GWAS methods

Trait	FASTmrEMMA	ISIS EM-BLASSO	mrMLM	pKWmEB	pLARmEB	GEMMA
LR	4	9	7	1	8	0
LH	7	14	5	5	5	0
FWR	5	16	7	9	35	0
DWR	3	23	6	65	0	63
BS	12	19	18	8	39	14

LR: main root length; LH: length of hypocotyls of healthy seedlings after treatments with control; FWR: the fresh weights of roots; DWR: dry weights of roots; BS: the biomass of seedlings.

Table 6. The significantly associated SNPs and their previously reported genes for five flowering traits in *Arabidopsis* using six GWAS methods

Trait	Chr	Position (bp)	Genome-wide association studies				Comparative genomics analysis		
			Effect	LOD	r ² (%)	Method	Gene	ID	References
LN10	1	848012	-0.0083	6.2556	0.0808	pLARmEB	BRN2	AT1G03457	Kim et al. (2013)
	1	1205598	0.0560	5.9390	1.1461	ISIS EM-BLASSO	CRY2	AT1G04400	Endo et al. (2007)
	1	3539585	0.0077	4.7995	0.0333	pLARmEB	ACLA-1	AT1G10670	Fatland et al. (2005)
	1	8276169	-0.0595	4.4830	0.6183	ISIS EM-BLASSO	RPL27AB	AT1G23290	Szakonyi et al. (2011)
	1	10700018	0.0071	2.0596	0.0788	pLARmEB	ARF6	AT1G30330	Nagpal et al. (2005)
	1	11040645	0.0177	10.4470	0.2023	pLARmEB	UFO, SUF4	AT1G30950	Schmid et al. (2005), Bao et al. (2011)
	2	16235384	0.0037	2.2324	0.0071	pLARmEB	HTA8	AT2G38810	Choi et al. (2007)
	3	586872	-0.0161	12.6578	0.4744	pLARmEB	IPP2	AT3G02780	Phillips et al. (2008)
	3	22957095	-0.0551	4.2873	2.1526	mrMLM	NGA2	AT3G61970	Alvarez et al. (2006)
	3	23294580	0.0090	9.3793	0.0745	pLARmEB	HULK3	AT3G63070	Jali et al. (2014)
	4	250918	0.0803	9.5658	4.8393	mrMLM	FRI	AT4G00650	Lee et al. (1993)
	4	625569	0.0059	2.5582	0.0604	pLARmEB	NGATHA4	AT4G01500	Alvarez et al. (2016)
	4	12729242	0.0689	3.8881	0.4874	ISIS EM-BLASSO	PGI1, TAR2	AT4G24620, AT4G24670, AT4G35900	Yu et al. (2000), Stepanova et al. (2008), Abe et al. (2005)
	4	12729242	0.0087	3.4812	0.0287	pLARmEB	PGI1, TAR2	AT4G24620, AT4G35900	Yu et al. (2000), Stepanova et al. (2008), Abe et al. (2005)
	4	17025163	0.0087	3.4812	0.0287	pLARmEB	FD	AT4G35900	Abe et al. (2005)
L16	5	4668076	-0.0621	6.2234	2.5922	pKWmEB	APRF1	AT5G14530	Kapolas, et al. (2016)
	5	3173183	0.0194	2.8883	0.5817	pLARmEB	FLC	AT5G10140	Edwards et al. (2006)
	5	21058897	-0.0021	5.5610	0.0052	pLARmEB	ATGA20OX2	AT5G51810	Rieu et al. (2007)
	1	8254033	-0.0608	4.2878	1.5912	pKWmEB	RPL27AB	AT1G23290	Szakonyi et al. (2011)
	1	10703613	-0.0084	2.1267	0.0155	pLARmEB	ARF6	AT1G30330	Nagpal et al. (2005)
L16	1	11058107	0.0663	3.0984	0.2269	ISIS EM-BLASSO	SUF4	AT1G30970	Kim et al. (2006)
	1	24345319	0.0141	4.6538	0.0391	pLARmEB	FT	AT1G65480	Xu et al. (2010)
	2	9810231	0.0898	3.9318	2.5186	pKWmEB	CKA4	AT2G23070	Wang et al. (2016)
	2	14309341	0.0901	3.3788	2.1263	mrMLM	SPL3, FES1	AT2G33810,	Cardon et al. 1997),

							AT2G33835	Ding et al.(2013)	
	2	14309341	0.0220	3.9715	0.1158	pLARmEB	SPL3, FES1	AT2G33810, AT2G33835	Cardon et al. 1997), Ding et al.(2013)
	3	18925809	-0.1099	7.2237	2.1063	ISIS EM-BLASSO	MNP	AT3G50870	Zhao et al. (2004)
	3	18925809	-0.3017	6.7489	3.9697	FASTmrEMMA	MNP	AT3G50870	Zhao et al. (2004)
	4	280774	0.0699	5.9618	1.5997	pLARmEB	FRI	AT4G00650	Lee et al. (1993)
	4	16312291	-0.0841	3.9232	0.7681	ISIS EM-BLASSO	MED25	AT4G34040	Iñigo et al. (2012)
	5	2264248	-0.1029	7.4188	2.1630	pLARmEB	ATGA20OX3	AT5G07200	Phillips et al. (1995)
	5	3188328	0.0544	8.5198	0.7609	pLARmEB	FLC	AT5G10140	Levy et al. (2002)
	5	4237362	-0.0383	5.7292	0.4316	pLARmEB	CORYNE	AT5G13290	Casamitjana et al. (2003)
	5	5189021	0.0289	4.3616	0.1197	pLARmEB	CO, COL1	AT5G15840, AT5G15850	Suarez-Lopez et al. (2001), Osterberg et al. (2002)
	5	8225049	0.0707	3.7280	0.5106	ISIS EM-BLASSO	ATPI4K	AT5G24240	Akhter et al. (2015)
	5	24008772	-0.1311	5.1978	3.1165	mrMLM	BOA	AT5G59570	Dai et al. (2011)
L22	1	2574860	0.1290	7.8843	1.2976	ISIS EM-BLASSO	TIL1	AT1G08260	Del Olmo et al. (2009)
	1	2598920	0.1408	6.1123	2.6773	mrMLM	TIL1	AT1G08260	Del Olmo et al. (2009)
	1	11030132	0.2238	8.8804	1.7489	ISIS EM-BLASSO	UFO,SUF4	AT1G30950, AT1G30970	Durfee et al(2003), Kim et al. (2006)
	1	11030132	0.0290	3.4487	0.0428	pLARmEB	UFO,SUF4	AT1G30950, AT1G30970	Durfee et al(2003), Kim et al. (2006)
	1	17342810	0.1243	4.0327	2.0802	pKWmEB	GAMMA CA2	AT1G47260	Fernando et al. (2009)
	1	19628400	-0.0816	3.9418	0.7034	ISIS EM-BLASSO	HTA9	AT1G52740	Choi et al. (2007)
	1	19629918	-0.1192	5.1054	3.0716	mrMLM	HTA9	AT1G52740	Choi et al. (2007)
	1	19790829	-0.0977	5.0600	1.0531	pLARmEB	SPL4	AT1G53160	Jung et al. (2006)
	3	5141792	-0.0291	3.5227	0.0720	pLARmEB	SPL5	AT3G15270	Jung et al. (2006)
	3	22949227	-0.0708	2.9645	0.5155	ISIS EM-BLASSO	NAC066, NGA2	AT3G61910, AT3G61970	Mitsuda et al. (2005), Alvarez et al. 2006)
	3	22949227	-0.0416	4.7411	0.2598	pLARmEB	NGA2	AT3G61970	Alvarez et al. (2016)
	3	23090917	-0.2167	9.0511	3.2268	ISIS EM-BLASSO	SAF1	AT3G62440	Kim et al. (2011)
	5	3173183	0.1668	9.7057	5.2520	pKWmEB	FLC	AT5G10140	Levy et al. (2002)
	5	7870995	-0.0895	6.7905	1.1894	pLARmEB	STE14A	AT5G23320	Bracha-Drori et al. (2008)
	5	18470541	-0.1358	8.1875	1.9423	ISIS EM-BLASSO	GAS41	AT5G45600	Bieluszewski et al. (2015)

	5	18470541	-0.1195	8.9526	3.0857	mrMLM	GAS41	AT5G45600	Bieluszewski et al. (2015)
	5	18470541	-0.2850	4.7757	2.1403	FASTmrEMMA	GAS41	AT5G45600	Bieluszewski et al. (2015)
	5	18470541	-0.1084	6.3915	1.8116	pLARmEB	GAS41	AT5G45600	Bieluszewski et al. (2015)
FW	1	1698567	-0.0110	2.0627	0.6342	pLARmEB	5PTASE13, BT3	AT1G05630, AT1G05690	Ananieva et al. (2008), Du et al. (2004)
	2	6033337	0.0692	3.6152	1.0584	ISIS EM-BLASSO	AGL44	AT2G14210	Zhang et al. (1998)
	2	6033337	0.1885	5.6103	11.1876	mrMLM	AGL44	AT2G14210	Zhang et al. (1998)
	2	6033337	0.3411	6.2402	6.4354	FASTmrEMMA	AGL44	AT2G14210	Zhang et al. (1998)
	3	905000	-0.1823	3.2977	3.3609	FASTmrEMMA	WOX11	AT3G03660	Liu et al. (2014)
	3	1801701	0.0981	3.1040	6.4010	mrMLM	ATCHR12	AT3G06010	Mlynárová et al. (2007)
	4	11221316	0.1689	11.9222	6.3107	ISIS EM-BLASSO	GALT2	AT4G21060	Basu et al. (2015)
	4	17037606	1.23E-05	3.4253347	6.01E-08	ISIS EM-BLASSO	,CSDP1	AT4G35985, AT4G36020	Banerjee et al. (2013), Kim et al. (2006)
	5	6311508	0.0877	6.7039	3.5080	pKWmEB	BUD2	AT5G18930	Ge et al. (2006)
	5	20805091	0.1452	4.6737	1.9689	pKWmEB	THAS1	AT5G48010	Field, et al. (2008)
DW	1	22075948	0.0017	3.0722	0.0080	pLARmEB	AT1G59960		Jiang et al. (2007)
	2	6033337	0.0961	5.4933	2.8411	ISIS EM-BLASSO	AT2G14210	AGL44	Zhang et al. (1998)
	2	6033337	0.3150	4.5493	7.6340	FASTmrEMMA	AT2G14210	AGL44	Zhang et al. (1998)
	3	10177824	-0.0320	3.3829	2.5964	pLARmEB	AT3G27460	SGF29a	Kaldis et al. (2010)
	3	21277841	0.0243	2.6903	1.7339	pLARmEB	AT3G57530	CPK32	Choi et al. (2005)
	4	17022039	0.0888	6.9440	3.5386	ISIS EM-BLASSO	AT4G35910	CTU2,	Philipp et al. (2014)
	4	18444823	0.0034	2.2248	0.0192	pLARmEB	AT4G39730	PLAT1	Hyun et al. (2014)
	5	6311508	0.0837	6.2769	4.4462	ISIS EM-BLASSO	AT5G18930	BUD2	Ge et al. (2006)
	5	14638890	0.0862	7.8725	4.7135	ISIS EM-BLASSO	AT5G37055	SEF	Choi et al. (2007)

LN10, LN16, LN22: leaf number at a flowering time at 10 °C, 16 °C, and 22 °C, respectively. FW: fresh weight; DW: dry weight

Table 7. The significantly associated SNPs and their previously reported genes for five quantitative traits in *Soybean datasets* in 2014 and 2015 with salt (NaCl) treatment using six GWAS methods

Trait	Chr.	Position (Bp)	Genome-Wide Association Studies					Candidate genes	Arabidopsis homologs	Functional Annotation	Ref
			Effect	LOD	r2 (%)	Method	Year				
LR-NaCl	2	5973085	-5.622	3.443	1.868	pLARmEB	2014	Glyma.02g067700	AT3G02050	K ⁺ transmembrane transporter	
	13	27798307	0.277	6.733	2.974	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2009	Glyma.13g162900	AT5G20380	transmembrane transport	
	14	8727726	0.137	3.352	1.506	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2014	Glyma.14g093900	AT5G11800	solute/H ⁺ antiporter activity	
	17	4008933	-0.223	3.744	2.984	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2014	Glyma.17g052400 Glyma.17g052500	AT4G29810 AT1G17550	MAP kinase kinase 2 catalytic activity	
LH-NaCl	17	3563319	0.235	4.345	2.078	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2010	Glyma.17g047300 (GmDREB2)	AT1G19210	DREB transcription factor	Phang 2008
	18	1690520	0.219	3.996	3.239	ISISEM-BLASSO	2014	Glyma.18g023000	AT2G13620	Na ⁺ /H ⁺ exchanger family	
	3	37366652	-0.616	5.754	13.813	ISISEM-BLASSO /pLARmEB	2009	Glyma.03g157800 (GmCaM9-4)	AT3G22930	Ca ²⁺ binding	Ren 2016
FWR-NaCl	17	41448838	0.501	5.107	4.316	ISISEM-BLASSO	2014	Glyma.17g261700	AT4G35090	oxidation-reduction process	
	1	4309825	-0.001	4.826		pLARmEB	2014	Glyma.01g040000	AT1G10360	Glutathione S-transferase	
	1	4309825/ 4325636	- 0.001~0.002	4.83~15.47		pLARmEB	2014	Glyma.01g040200	AT1G10360	Glutathione S-transferase	
	2	12096757	-0.0014	4.3451	2.579	pKWmEB	2009	Glyma.02g121800	AT2G03720	response to stress	
	2	12668957	0.001	6.318		pLARmEB	2014	Glyma.02g126100	AT3G30530	bZIP transcription factor	
	3	45380341				pLARmEB	2014	Glyma.03g260200	AT1G01140	Serine/threonine protein kinase	Zhu 2016
	4	11276797				pLARmEB	2010	Glyma.04g107500 (GmGST13)	AT3G09270	Glutathione S-transferase	Ji 2010
	4	5030664				pLARmEB	2014	Glyma.04g061500 (GmCIPK9)	AT5G25110	Serine/threonine protein kinase	Zhu 2016
	5	3664395	-0.002	4.08		pLARmEB	2009	Glyma.05g040700	AT5G26660	Myb transcription factor	
	6	12664811	0.001	3.421		pLARmEB	2009	Glyma.06g155500	AT1G77280	response to stress	
	6	6081400	0.017	8.244	3.566	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2010	Glyma.06g079800 (GmbZIP62)	AT5G24800	bZIP transcription factor	Liao 2008
	6	11900234	0.04	4.412	0.031	FASTmrEMMA	2010	Glyma.06g145300	AT5G05340	response to oxidative stress	

	6	11721239	0.028	5.223	5.999	mrMLM	2010	Glyma.06g143800	AT2G40540	K ⁺ transmembrane transport
	6	15552249	-0.012	3.472	1.997	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2009	Glyma.06g155200	AT5G17850	transmembrane transport
	14	655355	0.007	10.708		pLARmEB	2009	Glyma.14g007700	AT3G07770	response to stress
	15	49860450	-0.002	3.608		pLARmEB	2010	Glyma.15g264000	AT3G12720	Myb-like DNA-binding domain
								Glyma.15g264400	AT1G30870	response to oxidative stress
	15	14962700	-0.002	4.985		pLARmEB	2014	Glyma.15g168200	AT4G31550	WRKY DNA -binding domain
	16	32882299	0.003	4.369		pLARmEB	2009	Glyma.16g168400	AT1G43700	bZIP transcription factor
	16	36323725	0.013	6.308	1.936	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2010	Glyma.16g202200	AT4G05200	Salt stress response
	16	32495843	-0.001	6.068	0.061	pLARmEB	2014	Glyma.16g165900	AT5G64740	cellulose synthase (UDP-forming) activity
	17	3396743	-0.001	4.003		pLARmEB	2014	Glyma.17g045300	AT3G43230	FYVE zinc finger
	17	38650676	-0.009 ~ -0.01	2.87~3.42	1.45~2.01	ISIS EM-BLASSO /pKWmEB	2015	Glyma.17g231900	AT5G65790	MYB-LIKE DNA-BINDING PROTEIN MYB
	18	16296555 /16300753	-0.02 ~ 0.02	2.57 ~ 8.41	0.04~1.40	ISIS EM-BLASSO /mrMLM/pKWmEB	2010	Glyma.18g124700	AT5G15130	WRKY DNA -binding domain
	18	3965322	0.008	12.934	1.195	pKWmEB, 2010	2010	Glyma.18g046100/Glyma.18g046200/Glyma.18g046300	AT1G70520	Salt stress response
DWR -NaCl	1	42300569	-0.01	3.717	4.086	mrMLM	2009	Glyma.01g122800	AT3G51860	Ca ²⁺ /H ⁺ antiporter VCX1 and related proteins
	2	42365117	-0.002	5.035	2.034	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2009	Glyma.02g236200	AT2G40620	bZIP transcription factor
	2	12096757	12096757	-0.0014	4.3451			Glyma.02g121800	AT2G03720	response to stress
	3	34285550	-2.54E-05	5.154	5.00E-04	pKWmEB	2015	Glyma.03g128200	AT5G06950	bZIP transcription factor
	3	45380341	-0.001	2.425	0.5	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2010	Glyma.03g260200 (GmCIPK8)	AT1G01140	Serine/threonine protein kinase (Zhu 2016)
	4	11471448	-0.004	3.416	0.097	mrMLM	2014	Glyma.04g107900	AT3G53990	response to stress
	4	33071947	1.38E-02	5.85E-11		GEMMA	2015	Glyma.04g142700	AT5G17420	Cellulose synthase
	4	47809944	2.53E-05	5.4417	0.0012	pKWmEB	2015	Glyma.04g205400	AT1G10940	Serine/threonine protein kinase
	5	37809831	-0.001	3.371	1.797	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2009	Glyma.05g192400	AT5G64530	Sodium/hydrogen exchanger family
	6	5684370	-0.014	4.887	0.069	mrMLM	2009	Glyma.06g073200	AT5G11430	Predicted transcription factor DATF1
6	5684370	-0.014	4.887	0.069	mrMLM	2009	Glyma.06g073100	AT4G32600	Zinc finger, C3HC4 type (RING finger)	

	6	5684370	-0.014	4.887	0.069	mrMLM	2009	Glyma.06g074300	AT5G25560	Zn-finger protein	
	6	6081361	5.36E-05	3.6517	0.005	pKWmEB	2015	Glyma.06g079800 (GmbZIP62)	AT5G24800	bZIP transcription factor	Liao et al 2008
	6	3199037	-0.005	3.438	6.45	mrMLM	2015	Glyma.06g042100 (GmDREB2)	AT2G23340	regulation of transcription, DNA-templated	Phang , 2008
	14	47867182	0.011	3.053	0.05	mrMLM	2009	Glyma.14g213600	AT5G37660	Salt stress response/antifungal	
	14	46893280	-0.001	2.813	1.69	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2014	Glyma.14g204100	AT2G40620	bZIP transcription factor	
	14	7504616	0.001	2.782	2.644	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2014	Glyma.14g084700, (GmDREB1)	AT1G46768	regulation of transcription, DNA-templated	Phang , 2008
	15	3855027	0.016	3.011	0.037	mrMLM	2010	Glyma.15g049000	AT5G44080	bZIP transcription factor	
	15	3855027	0.016	3.011	3.735	mrMLM	2010	Glyma.15g048600	AT4G08500	MEKK and related serine/threonine protein kinases	
	15	15793353	0.002	4.714	6.188	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2015	Glyma.15g172500	AT1G72770	Protein phosphatase 2C	
	16	6265535	-5.78E-05	4.6855	0.0052	pKWmEB	2015	Glyma.16g063200	AT5G40760	glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase activity	
	18	16296555	0.001	6.639	2.812	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2010	Glyma.18g124700	AT5G15130	WRKY DNA -binding domain	
	18	7800228	0.001	4.607	2.781	pKWmEB	2010	Glyma.18g081200	AT4G26640	WRKY DNA-binding protein	
	20	254800	-1.53E-05	3.283	3.00E-04	pKWmEB		Glyma.20g002000	AT4G00370	transmembrane transport	
BS-NaCl	2	1200913	0.003	7.105		pLARmEB,	2010	Glyma.02g013100/Glyma.02g013500	AT3G62550/AT4G02110	response to stress/PHD-finger	
	2	42889680	0.018	5.213	1.821	FASTmrEMMA	2009	Glyma.02g240600	AT1G78380	Glutathione S-transferase	
	2	13638052	-0.01 ~ -0.02	2.59:5.86	0.06-0.77	ISIS EM-BLASSO/mrMLM	2014	Glyma.02g131700	AT1G49720	bZIP transcription factor	
	2	44029773	0	1.678	0	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2014	Glyma.02g253100	AT3G55730	MYB-like DNA-binding protein MYB	
	3	44598642	0.002	5.538		pLARmEB	2010	Glyma.03g250600	AT3G23250	MYB-like DNA-binding protein MYB	
	5	31582334	0.01 ~ 0.102	3.34 ~ 8.94	0.046 ~ 0.40	ISIS EM-BLASSO/FASTmrEMMA	2010	Glyma.05g122400	AT1G03970	bZIP transcription factor	
	5	38166911	0.007	2.677	1.056	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2014	Glyma.05g197700	AT1G10940	Serine/threonine protein kinase	
	6	1310389	-0.005	3.9996		pLARmEB	2009	Glyma.06g017900	AT4G35090	Catalase-related immune-responsive	
	13	28360967	-0.002	3.361		pLARmEB	2014	Glyma.13g170000	AT3G01460	PHD-finger	

14	47867182	0.011	3.053	0.05	mrMLM	2009	Glyma.14g213600	AT5G37660	Salt stress response/antifungal
14	45957917	-0.013	1.502	0.739	ISIS EM-BLASSO/mrMLM	2010	Glyma.14g194800	AT5G58610	PHD-finger
14	46844001	-0.011	4.854	0.027	FASTmrEMMA	2014	Glyma.14g204100	AT5G13080	bZIP transcription factor
15	3855027	0.016	3.011	0.037	mrMLM	2010	Glyma.15g049000	AT5G44080	bZIP transcription factor
15	3855027	0.016	3.011	3.735	mrMLM	2010	Glyma.15g048600	AT4G08500	MAPK/ERK kinase kinase
15	15793353	0.004~0.02	3.40 ~13.56	5.99~?	pLARmEB/mrMLM/pLARmEB	2015/2 014	Glyma.15g172500	AT1G72770	Serine/threonine protein phosphatase
17	39450868	0.006	3.18	0.904	ISIS EM-BLASSO	2014	Glyma.17g239200	AT4G24240	WRKY DNA -binding domain
17	15319513	0.007	3.196	0.02	mrMLM	2015	Glyma.17g167100	AT2G23290	Myb-like DNA-binding domain
18	3427487	-0.014	3.871	0.012	FASTmrEMMA	2009	Glyma.18g040700	AT5G16600	MYB-like DNA-binding protein MYB
18	3427487/346 2152	-0.004 ~ - 0.01	3.18~3. 87	0.0001 ~0.01	FASTmrEMMA/pLARmEB	2009	Glyma.18g040800	AT5G37660	Salt stress response/antifungal
18	6705051	0.07 ~ 0.08	3.1E-08 ~16.18	0.11~ 11.16	mrMLM/GEMMA/ISISEM-BLASSO/ISIS EM-BLASSO/mrMLM/GEMMA,/FASTm rEM M A/GEMMA	2010/2 014/20 15	Glyma.18g071600	AT5G23810	MYB-like DNA-binding protein MYB
20	45851691/45 832145	-0.01~ - 0.01	5.67 ~ 6.34	1.86 ~ 1.92	ISIS EM-BLASSO /pKWmEB/ISIS EM-BLASSO	2014/2 015	Glyma.20g223300	AT1G09770	MYB-like DNA-binding protein MYB

LR: main root length; LH: length of hypocotyls of healthy seedlings after treatments with control; FWR: the fresh weights of roots; DWR: dry weights of roots; BS: the biomass of seedlings.

Table S1. Significantly associated SNPs for five flowering traits in *Arabidopsis* using six GWAS methods

Trait	Chr	Position (bp)	Genome-wide association studies				Trait	Chr	Position (bp)	Genome-wide association studies			
			Effect	LOD	r ² (%)	Method				Effect	LOD	r ² (%)	Method
LN16	1	2826611	0.1143	6.9790	1.4610	ISIS EM-BLASSO	LN10	1	848012	-0.0083	6.2556	0.0808	pLARmEB
	1	2826611	0.2041	14.1597	8.2629	mrMLM		1	1205598	0.0560	5.9390	1.1461	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	2826611	0.3383	7.3331	3.1966	FASTmrEMMA		1	3539585	0.0077	4.7995	0.0333	pLARmEB
	1	2828062	0.0259	4.9453	0.2179	pLARmEB		1	4610135	0.0011	11.6204	0.0014	pLARmEB
	1	6254553	-0.0319	3.4852	0.3084	pLARmEB		1	4974673	0.0143	2.3339	0.3814	pLARmEB
	1	7447241	-0.0709	3.7361	1.0159	pKWmEB		1	8276169	-0.0595	4.4830	0.6183	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	7447241	-0.1702	7.4792	4.7438	mrMLM		1	10389636	-0.0236	12.7628	0.3162	pLARmEB
	1	7884838	0.0969	8.0947	1.8758	ISIS EM-BLASSO		1	10700018	0.0071	2.0596	0.0788	pLARmEB
	1	8254033	-0.0608	4.2878	1.5912	pKWmEB		1	11040645	0.0177	10.4470	0.2023	pLARmEB
	1	10703613	-0.0084	2.1267	0.0155	pLARmEB		1	11527747	0.0365	4.3921	0.3658	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	10967379	-0.1248	5.3938	4.3318	mrMLM		1	11552066	0.0575	4.3065	2.3058	pKWmEB
	1	10967379	-0.0072	4.0272	0.0131	pLARmEB		1	11815705	0.0024	5.0642	0.0057	pLARmEB
	1	11058107	0.0663	3.0984	0.2269	ISIS EM-BLASSO		1	12283930	0.0079	2.1456	0.1213	pLARmEB
	1	11611866	-0.0734	5.6650	1.0899	ISIS EM-BLASSO		1	13002545	-0.0657	6.7465	1.2899	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	12081450	0.0674	3.1660	0.5212	ISIS EM-BLASSO		1	13223873	-0.0065	3.6194	0.0730	pLARmEB
	1	12178910	-0.0459	8.0354	0.6795	pLARmEB		1	16590690	0.0620	4.3119	1.7787	pKWmEB
	1	12341946	-0.1123	5.6045	4.0479	mrMLM		1	16842962	-0.0015	2.5016	0.0039	pLARmEB
	1	16849329	0.0702	3.5109	2.0002	pKWmEB		1	17356536	0.0275	9.3917	0.8090	pLARmEB
	1	19008105	-0.0493	2.7325	0.4286	ISIS EM-BLASSO		1	17381255	-0.0599	10.0887	1.8123	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	19008105	-0.2017	4.2456	1.7915	FASTmrEMMA		1	17381255	-0.0553	6.1301	3.1246	mrMLM
	1	19008105	-0.0411	4.1359	0.4800	pLARmEB		1	19008105	-0.0710	4.6109	3.1142	pKWmEB
	1	19502334	-0.2018	4.1207	2.0443	FASTmrEMMA		1	19451396	0.0525	4.5963	2.5833	mrMLM
	1	19502334	-0.0871	10.1270	2.4609	pLARmEB		1	20916058	0.0727	6.1819	3.2718	mrMLM
	1	20751452	0.1255	8.3562	1.8088	ISIS EM-BLASSO		1	21706367	0.0108	8.9855	0.2084	pLARmEB

	1	23754243	-0.0338	4.4407	0.2937	pLARmEB			1	22566061	0.0292	51.6454	0.7808	pLARmEB
	1	23782942	-0.0836	4.6998	2.4434	mrMLM			1	27064152	0.0123	2.5312	0.1386	pLARmEB
	1	23838832	-0.0609	3.8136	0.9509	pLARmEB			1	28286184	0.0028	5.1535	0.0077	pLARmEB
	1	24345319	0.0141	4.6538	0.0391	pLARmEB			2	747291	-0.0024	2.7615	0.0093	pLARmEB
	1	24925862	-0.0659	12.7192	1.2591	pLARmEB			2	2916675	0.0413	3.8645	1.6611	mrMLM
	2	882256	0.0508	7.1417	0.8154	pLARmEB			2	4334710	-0.0051	14.1810	0.0274	pLARmEB
	2	7907956	-0.0341	2.9486	0.2629	pLARmEB			2	5289140	0.0659	9.3774	1.7490	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	2	9195977	0.0734	4.1303	1.5604	pKWmEB			2	5289140	0.0598	5.4098	2.9068	mrMLM
	2	9195977	0.1494	10.1881	5.2324	mrMLM			2	5289140	0.0181	18.1378	0.4867	pLARmEB
	2	9810231	0.0898	3.9318	2.5186	pKWmEB			2	5484655	-0.0174	4.2569	0.4793	pLARmEB
	2	10831065	0.1239	8.1386	1.9384	pLARmEB			2	5508121	-0.0385	3.0213	2.0608	pLARmEB
	2	12930967	0.0927	5.0481	1.2460	ISIS EM-BLASSO			2	6910434	0.0187	58.2049	0.4802	pLARmEB
	2	12930967	0.1468	8.2891	6.8464	pKWmEB			2	9309635	-0.0013	3.9095	0.0014	pLARmEB
	2	13039458	0.0147	3.3016	0.0429	pLARmEB			2	9353477	-0.0610	4.5722	2.4002	pKWmEB
	2	14309341	0.0901	3.3788	2.1263	mrMLM			2	9353477	-0.0100	11.1542	0.1763	pLARmEB
	2	14309341	0.0220	3.9715	0.1158	pLARmEB			2	9355426	0.0032	3.5061	0.0193	pLARmEB
	2	17537123	-0.0061	2.4266	0.0100	pLARmEB			2	9684258	0.0080	2.3727	0.0781	pLARmEB
	3	3773232	0.0548	5.6155	0.6413	pLARmEB			2	9789315	-0.0713	10.1195	5.0014	mrMLM
	3	5377034	-0.0105	2.6511	0.0181	pLARmEB			2	10814762	-0.0100	6.1455	0.1806	pLARmEB
	3	5853930	0.2698	5.1744	2.1445	FASTmrEMMA			2	11583810	0.0040	6.2289	0.0092	pLARmEB
	3	5853930	0.0393	3.4891	0.2942	pLARmEB			2	13517766	-0.0013	11.2332	0.0032	pLARmEB
	3	9038885	-0.0306	4.9826	0.1544	pLARmEB			2	13535691	0.0011	6.4940	0.0018	pLARmEB
	3	10781137	-0.0936	7.4765	3.8893	pKWmEB			2	14853933	0.0095	2.1342	0.0993	pLARmEB
	3	13580488	0.0092	4.5251	0.0111	pLARmEB			2	15736997	-0.0124	4.0539	0.1352	pLARmEB
	3	14977430	0.0438	9.7266	0.4087	pLARmEB			2	16235384	0.0037	2.2324	0.0071	pLARmEB
	3	15772384	0.0011	2.0376	0.0004	pLARmEB			2	16931396	-0.0848	9.0979	5.5752	mrMLM
	3	15833892	-0.0429	6.1948	0.5917	pLARmEB			2	16988732	0.0051	4.3414	0.0167	pLARmEB

	3	16340961	0.0512	3.5796	1.1632	pKWmEB			2	19361051	-0.0544	5.8520	0.6833	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	18068801	-0.0721	2.2092	0.7664	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	81339	-0.0397	8.2587	1.7744	pLARmEB
	3	18068801	-0.1718	6.3236	7.7287	mrMLM			3	586872	-0.0161	12.6578	0.4744	pLARmEB
	3	18068801	-0.0641	3.6008	0.9787	pLARmEB			3	628386	0.0032	8.3423	0.0202	pLARmEB
	3	18925809	-0.1099	7.2237	2.1063	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	1571179	-0.0790	11.9686	6.0021	mrMLM
	3	18925809	-0.3017	6.7489	3.9697	FASTmrEMMA			3	2212293	-0.0015	4.3152	0.0041	pLARmEB
	3	21331560	-0.0329	5.4251	0.2817	pLARmEB			3	3119603	0.1339	4.3124	2.2986	FASTmrEMMA
	4	280774	0.0699	5.9618	1.5997	pLARmEB			3	4988517	-0.0018	2.5862	0.0017	pLARmEB
	4	317129	0.1197	7.1131	2.7258	pLARmEB			3	6049903	0.0117	3.9772	0.2152	pLARmEB
	4	419382	0.0927	4.9103	3.0681	pKWmEB			3	7549718	0.0100	4.8165	0.1909	pLARmEB
	4	429928	0.1691	10.9655	9.8257	mrMLM			3	10157704	0.0205	2.8280	0.2017	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	431648	0.0973	3.4611	0.9045	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	10157704	0.0092	2.4606	0.1505	pLARmEB
	4	431648	0.1730	15.9958	4.6243	pLARmEB			3	10772469	-0.0137	10.9796	0.3458	pLARmEB
	4	454542	0.1226	8.0146	2.7214	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	10781137	-0.0719	11.1377	5.5350	mrMLM
	4	481062	0.1826	3.0872	1.5869	FASTmrEMMA			3	10855686	-0.0403	3.3891	0.6910	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	500090	-0.0916	4.1207	2.4265	pKWmEB			3	10855686	-0.0836	9.5391	5.9988	mrMLM
	4	503615	0.0643	7.5209	1.3120	pLARmEB			3	10855686	-0.0098	2.0696	0.1510	pLARmEB
	4	519513	-0.0930	7.2825	1.7434	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	11673793	0.0357	4.7495	0.3812	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	1248265	0.0833	4.2374	2.5693	pKWmEB			3	11673793	0.0270	7.1876	0.8012	pLARmEB
	4	1292368	0.2640	5.8926	2.5273	FASTmrEMMA			3	12574975	-0.0091	3.8835	0.0502	pLARmEB
	4	1547099	-0.0257	2.9793	0.1939	pLARmEB			3	15557477	0.0453	4.2625	2.0212	mrMLM
	4	4144904	0.0828	3.6064	2.4185	mrMLM			3	18331626	-0.0023	16.6020	0.0102	pLARmEB
	4	4999078	0.1092	3.5560	0.9931	pLARmEB			3	20355912	0.0043	2.7048	0.0145	pLARmEB
	4	6272658	0.0681	4.5333	0.9107	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	21324998	-0.0389	3.3843	0.5434	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	6272658	0.1002	6.8370	4.3162	pKWmEB			3	21324998	-0.0820	10.5847	4.8584	mrMLM
	4	6275985	0.1306	6.9357	3.7431	mrMLM			3	22957095	-0.0551	4.2873	2.1526	mrMLM
	4	6902128	-0.0510	3.3722	0.3502	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	23294580	0.0090	9.3793	0.0745	pLARmEB

	4	6906363	-0.0816	6.2587	2.5463	pKWmEB			4	250918	0.0803	9.5658	4.8393	mrMLM
	4	7624364	-0.0647	4.8751	0.8435	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	412959	0.1202	20.0517	4.3213	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	7624364	-0.1923	5.5709	1.8653	FASTmrEMMA			4	425071	0.0847	6.9912	3.8307	pKWmEB
	4	7624364	-0.0327	4.0039	0.3493	pLARmEB			4	625569	0.0059	2.5582	0.0604	pLARmEB
	4	8289336	0.0297	3.3724	0.1669	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	643170	0.0132	10.8610	0.1953	pLARmEB
	4	8540491	0.0863	9.2124	2.1209	pLARmEB			4	657038	-0.0095	2.4949	0.1632	pLARmEB
	4	8541934	0.0496	3.6771	1.0661	pKWmEB			4	1446360	-0.1255	3.5257	1.9797	FASTmrEMMA
	4	15029421	0.0275	2.6881	0.0480	pLARmEB			4	5441209	-0.0091	5.1329	0.0614	pLARmEB
	4	15996750	-0.1151	4.9761	2.7685	mrMLM			4	5772745	0.0012	15.9619	0.0029	pLARmEB
	4	16312291	-0.0841	3.9232	0.7681	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	6107363	-0.0383	4.3019	0.6401	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	17335742	-0.2502	5.4809	2.3822	FASTmrEMMA			4	6682591	0.0019	6.7840	0.0036	pLARmEB
	4	17905389	-0.0010	3.4592	0.0001	pLARmEB			4	6861095	-0.0487	3.2185	1.3705	pKWmEB
	5	2264248	-0.1029	7.4188	2.1630	pLARmEB			4	6965943	0.0369	4.0959	0.4692	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	2551768	-0.1512	3.3906	3.7403	mrMLM			4	9479350	-0.0473	3.7203	1.5247	mrMLM
	5	3188328	0.0544	8.5198	0.7609	pLARmEB			4	12729242	0.0689	3.8881	0.4874	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	4237362	-0.0383	5.7292	0.4316	pLARmEB			4	12729242	0.0087	3.4812	0.0287	pLARmEB
	5	4611404	-0.0815	4.1220	0.6574	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	13165981	0.0161	7.1354	0.4405	pLARmEB
	5	4907894	0.0903	5.1231	3.3568	pKWmEB			4	13692807	-0.0012	2.0138	0.0009	pLARmEB
	5	5189021	0.0289	4.3616	0.1197	pLARmEB			4	14263080	-0.0269	2.6985	0.3723	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	6299730	0.1215	9.3344	2.6022	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	15079213	-0.0619	4.9809	0.8847	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	6299730	0.1172	7.4597	5.2955	pKWmEB			4	15079213	-0.0129	2.7673	0.1424	pLARmEB
	5	6299730	0.0782	3.4875	1.9124	mrMLM			4	15831127	-0.2389	8.3055	5.6630	FASTmrEMMA
	5	6299730	0.2649	6.8608	3.0902	FASTmrEMMA			4	15930436	-0.0250	2.1980	0.6491	pLARmEB
	5	6299730	0.0718	5.4156	1.4664	pLARmEB			4	16056494	-0.0703	13.5516	2.5227	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	6586086	-0.0834	4.8953	1.2980	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	16056494	-0.0770	11.2126	6.1003	mrMLM
	5	6586086	-0.2077	4.2843	2.0118	FASTmrEMMA			4	16056494	-0.0135	6.9288	0.3438	pLARmEB
	5	6586086	-0.0652	4.5476	1.2831	pLARmEB			4	16644567	-0.1771	7.2978	4.1604	FASTmrEMMA

	5	7191122	0.0683	3.5179	2.0332	pKWmEB			4	17025163	0.0030	11.3301	0.0159	pLARmEB
	5	8225049	0.0707	3.7280	0.5106	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	17330964	0.0401	5.0362	0.6854	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	10000122	0.1764	9.9634	8.1466	mrMLM			5	3173183	0.0194	2.8883	0.5817	pLARmEB
	5	10937132	0.1046	6.5382	3.4549	mrMLM			5	3645854	0.0123	10.5445	0.1394	pLARmEB
	5	17453912	0.0714	5.7006	2.0667	pKWmEB			5	4396931	-0.0264	11.7375	1.1950	pLARmEB
	5	17688358	-0.0924	7.4258	3.3861	pKWmEB			5	4409771	0.0514	4.3992	2.0800	mrMLM
	5	18530832	0.0809	4.9719	0.7883	pLARmEB			5	4668076	-0.0621	6.2234	2.5922	pKWmEB
	5	18546461	-0.0755	4.8388	0.9536	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	4867634	0.0389	4.7703	1.7474	pLARmEB
	5	18577269	-0.1242	10.8952	5.5832	pKWmEB			5	7704503	-0.0211	7.3602	0.8678	pLARmEB
	5	18583672	-0.2659	5.1400	2.1351	FASTmrEMMA			5	8738531	-0.0512	7.4116	1.2945	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	18583672	-0.0799	5.2705	1.2471	pLARmEB			5	8779356	-0.0011	6.3145	0.0023	pLARmEB
	5	18600041	-0.2070	4.3189	2.1203	FASTmrEMMA			5	8843388	-0.1768	5.8583	3.1014	FASTmrEMMA
	5	18600041	-0.0171	3.0732	0.0934	pLARmEB			5	9438948	-0.0537	5.3447	2.6488	mrMLM
	5	18773872	-0.0682	4.1832	2.0596	pKWmEB			5	9441899	-0.0424	4.8969	0.8399	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	18937735	0.0596	4.1442	1.5524	pKWmEB			5	11558366	-0.0243	4.2290	0.2965	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	21170093	0.0720	4.0935	0.7772	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	11558366	-0.1026	3.7151	1.3229	FASTmrEMMA
	5	21170093	0.0384	3.1630	0.4836	pKWmEB			5	11558366	-0.0290	22.5791	1.5562	pLARmEB
	5	21170093	0.0330	5.3956	0.2634	pLARmEB			5	11757074	0.0220	14.3775	0.9233	pLARmEB
	5	21638413	0.0367	5.5017	0.2002	pLARmEB			5	14243812	-0.0635	6.4036	3.4212	mrMLM
	5	21717239	0.2254	3.7680	1.2988	FASTmrEMMA			5	16913185	-0.0113	7.9776	0.2059	pLARmEB
	5	21953451	-0.1008	7.4826	1.6378	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	17332407	0.0062	17.9177	0.0537	pLARmEB
	5	21953451	-0.2140	4.5038	1.8446	FASTmrEMMA			5	17450382	-0.0888	11.1473	2.9314	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	24008772	-0.1311	5.1978	3.1165	mrMLM			5	17450382	-0.0667	5.1337	3.3353	mrMLM
	5	25120893	0.1054	9.0555	2.2716	pLARmEB			5	17450382	-0.1788	5.1206	2.9695	FASTmrEMMA
	5	26149222	0.0903	3.9203	2.5250	mrMLM			5	17450382	-0.0224	6.2241	0.6828	pLARmEB
LN22	1	2574860	0.1290	7.8843	1.2976	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	17469249	-0.0157	12.8433	0.3163	pLARmEB
	1	2598920	0.1408	6.1123	2.6773	mrMLM			5	18600041	-0.0629	7.8903	2.0466	ISIS EM-BLASSO

	1	2684894	-0.1284	4.6709	2.7577	pKWmEB			5	18600041	-0.0772	11.1977	6.2181	mrMLM
	1	2747091	-0.1585	6.4979	3.2385	mrMLM			5	18600041	-0.2474	11.5643	7.9124	FASTmrEMMA
	1	3876090	-0.1867	7.9412	6.4955	pKWmEB			5	18889224	-0.0429	5.1330	0.5213	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	3876090	-0.4206	6.2798	3.6567	FASTmrEMMA			5	21058897	-0.0021	5.5610	0.0052	pLARmEB
	1	7448217	-0.0898	3.1922	1.5223	pKWmEB			5	21675015	-0.1007	5.0906	2.9032	pKWmEB
	1	8309549	0.1460	9.1217	4.5709	mrMLM			5	21949524	-0.0800	9.8283	2.0142	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	8431829	-0.1842	6.2884	2.8324	mrMLM			5	22108492	0.0485	6.5681	1.2071	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	11030132	0.2238	8.8804	1.7489	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	22108492	0.0564	6.7921	3.2887	mrMLM
	1	11030132	0.0290	3.4487	0.0428	pLARmEB			5	22108492	0.1751	7.0498	3.9297	FASTmrEMMA
	1	16144780	0.2020	6.8660	1.3501	pLARmEB			5	24293886	0.0015	4.5297	0.0044	pLARmEB
	1	16250117	0.0786	4.2596	0.5863	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	25452177	0.0010	2.7054	0.0007	pLARmEB
	1	16590690	0.1393	4.6445	2.7352	mrMLM			5	26461574	-0.0464	3.9558	1.9741	mrMLM
	1	17342810	0.1243	4.0327	2.0802	pKWmEB			5	26605511	0.0532	3.1310	2.0091	pKWmEB
	1	17648940	-0.1502	7.5997	5.0001	pKWmEB			5	26605511	0.1667	5.1518	3.6619	FASTmrEMMA
	1	17648940	-0.2913	4.8656	2.0870	FASTmrEMMA		FW	1	1698567	-0.0110	2.0627	0.6342	pLARmEB
	1	18338021	0.0366	6.6468	0.0604	pLARmEB			1	15881329	0.1234	4.9036	7.6581	mrMLM
	1	18788653	-0.3094	5.6497	2.5157	FASTmrEMMA			1	15881329	0.1621	3.0682	2.3237	FASTmrEMMA
	1	19033015	-0.1948	8.0472	5.7791	mrMLM			1	17350849	0.0863	5.9548	2.9555	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	19628400	-0.0816	3.9418	0.7034	ISIS EM-BLASSO			1	17350849	0.0426	2.5363	9.3352	pLARmEB
	1	19629918	-0.1192	5.1054	3.0716	mrMLM			1	20089452	0.0530	4.2898	2.3896	pKWmEB
	1	19790829	-0.0977	5.0600	1.0531	pLARmEB			1	24966182	0.1021	6.9208	2.8673	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	23471480	-0.1821	9.1554	1.8191	ISIS EM-BLASSO			1	24966182	0.1495	9.6505	11.8533	pKWmEB
	1	23471480	-0.1166	3.9241	1.5295	mrMLM			1	26149607	-0.0301	7.7251	3.3659	pLARmEB
	2	80789	-0.0847	10.9941	0.7641	pLARmEB			2	2179293	-0.0811	6.5124	4.9341	pKWmEB
	2	3040783	-0.0055	4.2862	0.0046	pLARmEB			2	2369802	0.1447	3.1818	1.6306	FASTmrEMMA
	2	4720829	0.0936	3.9388	0.6827	ISIS EM-BLASSO			2	5077735	-0.1020	10.4121	4.2122	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	2	4720829	0.3271	4.9241	2.0856	FASTmrEMMA			2	6033337	0.0692	3.6152	1.0584	ISIS EM-BLASSO

	2	4720829	0.0920	4.5303	0.9654	pLARmEB			2	6033337	0.1885	5.6103	11.1876	mrMLM
	2	13168846	-0.4475	6.1376	3.7140	FASTmrEMMA			2	6033337	0.3411	6.2402	6.4354	FASTmrEMMA
	2	13183674	0.1514	8.4992	4.4281	mrMLM			2	7419914	0.1054	4.5010	7.3017	mrMLM
	3	3843401	-0.1355	3.0086	1.2872	pLARmEB			2	10273914	0.0060	2.3548	0.1147	pLARmEB
	3	3934169	0.1122	7.8354	1.6542	pLARmEB			2	18451472	0.1591	5.3165	9.9085	mrMLM
	3	5141792	-0.0291	3.5227	0.0720	pLARmEB			2	18451472	0.4030	6.9511	11.1709	FASTmrEMMA
	3	5568975	0.0359	4.0186	0.1614	pLARmEB			2	18451472	0.0433	3.6749	6.6888	pLARmEB
	3	5579959	-0.1414	4.4569	0.9944	ISIS EM-BLASSO			2	18469021	0.0787	3.3492	1.4585	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	5579959	-0.1687	5.9829	2.0696	pLARmEB			3	905000	-0.1823	3.2977	3.3609	FASTmrEMMA
	3	5607052	-0.1853	15.4700	5.4959	mrMLM			3	1801701	0.0981	3.1040	6.4010	mrMLM
	3	8953954	-0.0994	3.9792	0.9922	pLARmEB			3	9157588	0.0923	3.5290	6.6417	pKWmEB
	3	10781137	-0.1140	7.3112	2.8130	mrMLM			3	11124275	0.0662	6.3860	2.0266	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	11249835	-0.1561	4.5501	0.9916	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	11562666	0.1316	4.6901	8.9504	mrMLM
	3	11504515	-0.0743	3.3762	0.5009	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	11626543	0.0113	2.5067	0.7569	pLARmEB
	3	12865757	-0.1076	5.9267	1.1822	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	12447347	0.0975	4.7035	6.2460	mrMLM
	3	12865757	-0.0983	4.1310	2.2254	pKWmEB			3	12789252	0.1619	4.5126	2.7427	FASTmrEMMA
	3	12865757	-0.1521	11.9897	4.8503	mrMLM			3	13477059	0.0111	2.7840	0.5333	pLARmEB
	3	12865757	-0.3169	6.4039	2.5631	FASTmrEMMA			3	15393893	0.0773	4.6232	1.7205	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	15970445	-0.0996	3.9591	2.1406	pKWmEB			3	15539637	0.0114	2.8376	0.7829	pLARmEB
	3	15986294	0.0987	4.1736	0.7479	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	22553571	-0.0171	3.1243	1.0479	pLARmEB
	3	15986294	0.1140	3.6983	2.2489	pKWmEB			4	6063180	0.0601	4.4569	1.1249	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	18081978	-0.1242	5.9609	3.5768	pKWmEB			4	6345558	-0.1133	6.0827	3.6902	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	22949227	-0.0708	2.9645	0.5155	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	11221316	0.1689	11.9222	6.3107	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	22949227	-0.0416	4.7411	0.2598	pLARmEB			4	13064038	-0.0198	4.7677	2.0503	pLARmEB
	3	23090917	-0.2167	9.0511	3.2268	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	17037606	0.0000	2.4253	0.0000	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	234070	0.1614	6.4115	5.6960	pKWmEB			4	17345847	0.0137	3.1259	0.4290	pLARmEB
	4	317129	-0.4120			GEMMA			5	2260274	0.0549	4.7990	2.6835	pKWmEB

	4	369042	-0.0016	2.1795	0.0002	pLARmEB			5	5423605	0.0618	3.6658	3.4288	pKWmEB
	4	429928	0.1975	12.6391	3.9269	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	6311508	0.0877	6.7039	3.5080	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	429928	-0.3720			GEMMA			5	6311508	0.1073	4.4329	10.1367	pKWmEB
	4	429928	0.2055	10.6067	9.5790	pKWmEB			5	8703098	0.0123	2.7753	0.7725	pLARmEB
	4	429928	0.2379	22.8822	11.6902	mrMLM			5	14595054	-0.0769	6.5436	1.7711	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	429928	0.3422	4.4975	2.9480	FASTmrEMMA			5	14595054	-0.1080	7.9108	6.7326	pKWmEB
	4	429928	0.0781	3.7299	0.8975	pLARmEB			5	15074338	0.0309	5.0165	2.9153	pLARmEB
	4	615135	-0.0436	2.3043	0.1945	pLARmEB			5	15417254	0.0996	3.1819	1.1609	FASTmrEMMA
	4	797876	-0.3324	5.7205	2.0129	FASTmrEMMA			5	19472289	0.0684	3.5364	3.0971	pKWmEB
	4	1261211	-0.1975	17.3529	3.8354	pLARmEB			5	20805091	0.1452	4.6737	1.9689	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	1331695	-0.0784	2.3028	0.5017	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	21884601	0.0898	5.6414	5.1777	pKWmEB
	4	4866310	0.1132	3.6114	2.4760	mrMLM			5	22303217	0.1342	10.2596	4.4831	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	5018803	0.1444	3.9925	1.0040	pLARmEB			5	22303217	0.0812	3.2251	3.1693	pKWmEB
	4	5742291	-0.1493	4.2053	2.8386	pKWmEB			5	22303217	0.1676	4.3788	9.9584	mrMLM
	4	5742291	-0.1208	5.6653	1.6921	mrMLM		DW	1	8948655	0.0016	2.3013	0.0051	pLARmEB
	4	5742291	-0.3778	4.8110	2.0166	FASTmrEMMA			1	16670060	0.0062	3.2352	0.0923	pLARmEB
	4	6040154	0.0610	3.0580	0.7466	pKWmEB			1	17350849	0.1162	9.5858	7.4605	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	8062139	-0.1282	5.1096	2.8629	mrMLM			1	17350849	0.1672	3.3340	5.9700	mrMLM
	4	8540043	-0.0836	2.7081	1.0503	pLARmEB			1	17350849	0.2508	5.4862	8.6855	FASTmrEMMA
	4	8561967	0.0868	3.2305	1.7279	pKWmEB			1	20800890	0.1507	3.7462	11.4644	pKWmEB
	4	8561967	0.1424	10.6781	4.2321	mrMLM			1	22075948	0.0017	3.0722	0.0080	pLARmEB
	4	8949791	-0.1000	4.1556	0.5320	ISIS EM-BLASSO			1	25049818	0.0096	2.8880	0.1050	pLARmEB
	4	8949791	-0.1548	5.3387	2.8731	pKWmEB			2	6033337	0.0961	5.4933	2.8411	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	10448135	0.0014	2.7884	0.0002	pLARmEB			2	6033337	0.3150	4.5493	7.6339	FASTmrEMMA
	4	15065876	-0.0715	7.5412	0.7605	pLARmEB			2	18443679	0.1327	5.8983	3.9318	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	15645842	-0.1800	6.9443	2.0348	ISIS EM-BLASSO			2	18451472	0.2696	4.6373	6.9554	FASTmrEMMA
	4	15941850	-0.1284	3.8329	2.9861	pKWmEB			3	6320366	0.0805	6.3196	3.7099	ISIS EM-BLASSO

	4	15959303	-0.1924	8.8404	3.0579	pLARmEB			3	10177824	-0.0320	3.3829	2.5964	pLARmEB
	4	16535446	0.0627	2.5129	0.4133	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	11124275	0.0691	5.5177	3.0697	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	16535446	0.2081	3.1091	1.1383	FASTmrEMMA			3	11125697	-0.1698	4.1197	4.3145	FASTmrEMMA
	4	16689198	-0.0732	4.9185	0.8276	pLARmEB			3	11754760	0.0998	4.3602	7.5372	pKWmEB
	4	16774064	-0.0982	3.2175	1.4561	pLARmEB			3	11807742	0.0014	2.1095	0.0087	pLARmEB
	4	17335742	-0.1408	7.0503	1.5458	ISIS EM-BLASSO			3	15393893	0.2737	5.6361	7.4888	FASTmrEMMA
	4	17335742	-0.1895	9.5096	5.7448	mrMLM			3	15797653	0.0053	4.9088	0.1019	pLARmEB
	4	17335742	-0.2956	3.3910	1.7031	FASTmrEMMA			3	21277841	0.0243	2.6903	1.7339	pLARmEB
	4	17335742	-0.1034	7.7312	1.2177	pLARmEB			4	2197874	-0.0468	3.3012	5.2411	pLARmEB
	5	441370	-0.1642	4.0023	3.5324	pKWmEB			4	6915947	0.0238	2.1914	2.4755	pLARmEB
	5	3058028	-0.0123	3.0348	0.0099	pLARmEB			4	17022039	0.0627	4.5215	2.5258	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	3173183	0.1668	9.7057	5.2520	pKWmEB			4	17217496	-0.0736	3.1354	3.4889	pKWmEB
	5	4660138	-0.1528	6.8342	1.5718	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	18444823	0.0034	2.2248	0.0192	pLARmEB
	5	5423605	-0.1212	6.3966	3.3930	pKWmEB			5	1290861	-0.0116	3.9996	0.4684	pLARmEB
	5	6424077	-0.1535	6.1482	1.1338	pLARmEB			5	6311508	0.0837	6.2769	4.4462	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	6546259	-0.0639	2.3232	0.3370	pLARmEB			5	12378230	0.2320	5.2858	8.6873	FASTmrEMMA
	5	7870995	-0.0895	6.7905	1.1894	pLARmEB			5	14252806	-0.0410	3.0103	0.9619	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	12782295	0.1301	5.7829	1.0885	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	14638890	0.0862	7.8725	4.7135	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	13758499	-0.0012	2.2258	0.0002	pLARmEB			5	15130377	-0.0031	2.3827	0.0236	pLARmEB
	5	14595810	0.0938	4.1276	1.5336	mrMLM			5	16823504	0.0888	6.9440	3.5386	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	14595810	0.0623	9.5747	0.4815	pLARmEB			5	20805091	0.1044	3.3037	1.4143	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	16826645	0.1086	6.1714	1.1597	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	22303217	0.0901	4.6509	2.8125	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	17963793	0.1216	6.3639	3.4527	pKWmEB			5	22303217	0.0793	3.0403	2.5390	pKWmEB
	5	18222106	0.1437	11.0818	4.4613	mrMLM		LN22	5	18470541	-0.1084	6.3915	1.8116	pLARmEB
	5	18222106	0.0197	3.2646	0.0594	pLARmEB			5	18599929	-0.0668	4.1638	0.6195	pLARmEB
	5	18470541	-0.1358	8.1875	1.9423	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	22108492	0.1410	12.3896	4.1657	mrMLM
	5	18470541	-0.1195	8.9526	3.0857	mrMLM			5	25382487	0.3654	5.9497	2.9012	FASTmrEMMA

	5	18470541	-0.2850	4.7757	2.1403	FASTmrEMMA			5	25382487	0.0997	9.0355	1.2629	pLARmEB
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LN10, LN16, LN22: leaf number at a flowering time at 10 °C, 16 °C, and 22 °C, respectively. FW: fresh weight; DW: dry weight

Table S2. Significantly associated SNPs for five quantitative traits in soybean water treatment datasets in 2014 using six GWAS methods

Trait	Chr	Position (bp)	Genome-wide association studies				Trait	Chr	Position (bp)	Genome-wide association studies			
			Effect	LOD	r ² (%)	Method				Effect	LOD	r ² (%)	Method
LR	1	41705335	0.3729	6.5896	3.4576	ISIS EM-BLASSO	FWR	1	674489	0.0827	5.3963	0.0459	FASTmrEMMA
	1	49841779	-0.2973	5.0459	2.3143	ISIS EM-BLASSO		2	35385564	0.018876	3.393589	1.799	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	2	4635144	0.6553	3.7994	0.0207	FASTmrEMMA		2	44943084	0.0305	3.8949	0.0387	mrMLM
	2	4635144	0.3262	3.5287	2.4786	pLARmEB		2	49146815	-0.0497	4.01	0.0314	FASTmrEMMA
	3	44515929	0.2956	4.1816	1.9424	ISIS EM-BLASSO		3	4645510	-0.01497	3.599992	1.5367	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	5813235	-0.3003	3.9551	5.1259	pLARmEB		4	38189565	0.019237	3.742034	1.8479	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	3552232	-0.5625	4.1069	6.9836	ISIS EM-BLASSO		4	44194519	-0.01934	4.076282	1.8683	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	6917225	0.3182	5.9078	2.4469	ISIS EM-BLASSO		4	3651534	-0.0286	4.0017	5.9327	pKWmEB
	4	3552232	-0.7861	4.1708	0.1356	mrMLM		4	44194519	-0.01	4.0882	0.5592	pKWmEB
	4	9209088	0.5695	4.9776	0.0524	mrMLM		4	44194519	-0.0354	4.1473	0.0567	mrMLM
	4	39064792	-0.576	3.3685	0	mrMLM		5	2436175	1.64E-05	3.3979	1.89E-06	pKWmEB
	4	6938688	0.2186	3.3316	4.2275	pLARmEB		5	3322804	-0.0401	3.8434	0.0265	FASTmrEMMA
	4	9209088	0.3639	4.5843	4.8748	pLARmEB		5	38490610	0.0391	3.078	0.0241	FASTmrEMMA
	5	32409023	0.3061	4.937	2.4673	ISIS EM-BLASSO		7	7598102	0.047858	4.192161	2.6951	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	34936229	0.3111	3.7069	1.0674	ISIS EM-BLASSO		7	8025102	-0.01668	3.296464	1.4201	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	32346153	0.6275	3.6809	0.0234	FASTmrEMMA		7	7673615	0.0376	5.5204	0.0787	mrMLM
	5	32346153	0.243	3.2093	3.4556	pLARmEB		7	7673615	0.0606	5.9819	0.0495	FASTmrEMMA
	6	20836783	-0.3537	2.7663	1.5213	ISIS EM-BLASSO		8	591361	0.058636	5.42409	6.8404	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	7	17318295	-0.536	9.6337	7.0332	ISIS EM-BLASSO		8	5128158	-0.0265	7.9034	4.5429	pKWmEB
	7	17318295	-0.4421	5.0662	5.3969	pKWmEB		9	42415915	0.0023	3.1173	0.0277	pKWmEB
	7	17318295	-0.5399	7.7354	0.071	mrMLM		9	40787234	-3.17E-05	3.409	7.98E-06	pKWmEB

	7	9805167	0.631	5.9692	0.0644	mrMLM			9	36827262	-0.0278	4.3985	0.0441	mrMLM
	7	5056430	0.9521	6.8341	0.0663	mrMLM			10	10923040	0.012624	2.262364	0.9638	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	7	17318295	-0.9402	6.1358	0.0427	FASTmrEMMA			10	46596686	-0.02834	6.46775	3.4804	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	7	9805167	0.508	5.3346	3.2755	pLARmEB			10	10923040	0.026	3.9635	0.037	mrMLM
	7	17318295	-0.4533	6.8262	1.9006	pLARmEB			11	11316463	-0.02014	4.792713	2.5012	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	8	7535164	0.5379	3.4556	2.3141	ISIS EM-BLASSO			14	3309359	-0.02718	2.711096	1.4692	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	8	9323077	0.3197	4.2275	2.1403	ISIS EM-BLASSO			14	6400658	-0.04849	8.025964	5.4824	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	8	9323077	0.3434	3.2755	2.7836	pKWmEB			14	6400658	-0.0481	5.0883	0.049	mrMLM
	8	9324946	0.3071	3.0993	0.0208	mrMLM			16	29225627	-0.02196	3.048431	1.4376	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	8	9324946	0.3235	6.4129	1.2564	pLARmEB			16	29225627	-0.0169	3.6597	0.949	pKWmEB
	10	4486544	-0.4693	3.4001	3.0894	pKWmEB			17	8592762	0.021413	3.591372	1.5755	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	10	3592606	0.4773	6.3019	0.7007	pLARmEB			19	3430843	-0.05057	5.09322	4.8638	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	12	33110575	-0.5213	4.3824	3.9603	pLARmEB			19	9598903	0.020915	3.590954	1.5031	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	12	8033666	-0.345	6.7967	2.7335	pLARmEB			19	31381851	0.0017	3.185	0.012	pKWmEB
	14	1190068	0.1639	2.4786	0.7007	ISIS EM-BLASSO			19	23319225	0.0486	3.3643	0.0204	FASTmrEMMA
	14	17056847	-0.3628	2.4249	1.2564	ISIS EM-BLASSO			20	2061117	-0.02574	3.280598	2.5604	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	14	1425656	0.4161	5.4929	0.0448	mrMLM			20	23995652	-0.2255	5.179	0.2325	mrMLM
	14	48673430	0.4957	6.5349	0.0528	mrMLM	BS		1	16257069	-0.0088	3.6077	2.1145	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	14	48673430	0.2019	2.8209	9.6337	pLARmEB			1	51528827	0.0204	9.3291	3.4411	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	14	1425698	0.2756	4.6717	5.8503	pLARmEB			1	6458540	0.0197	6.442	0.0399	mrMLM
	15	10395231	0.3262	5.1259	2.7335	ISIS EM-BLASSO			1	581883	0.0113	3.7229	0.0226	mrMLM
	15	10395231	0.4337	5.0623	0.048	mrMLM			3	29644613	0.0092	4.3613	2.1673	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	15	10395231	0.6425	4.0696	0.0235	FASTmrEMMA			3	29644613	0.0116	3.978	5.5739	pKWmEB
	16	5232513	-0.3812	3.8455	0.0351	mrMLM			3	29644613	0.019	3.6259	0.0197	FASTmrEMMA
	16	3571156	-0.6311	2.9473	0.0102	FASTmrEMMA			4	10193031	0.0078	2.7419	0.9214	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	16	5232513	-0.492	2.9346	0.0127	FASTmrEMMA			4	40160663	-0.0031	2.2463	0.2367	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	16	5232513	-0.349	5.626	3.4001	pLARmEB			4	36767989	0.0185	7.4582	0.0978	mrMLM
	18	10686197	-0.2691	3.9603	1.9006	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	29123824	0.0214	3.0624	0.0214	FASTmrEMMA
	18	10686197	-0.3115	3.2682	0.0253	mrMLM			5	30060880	0.0154	4.5767	2.5571	ISIS EM-BLASSO

	18	10686197	-0.5223	3.2308	0.0163	FASTmrEMMA			5	38490643	0.0049	3.4277	0.6534	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	18	10686197	-0.2401	3.9111	2.4249	pLARmEB			5	38425844	0.0085	3.8696	0.0275	mrMLM
	20	1320458	-0.3819	4.8748	2.3372	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	3302544	-0.0192	4.2433	0.0232	FASTmrEMMA
	20	27518350	-0.3932	5.8503	2.9189	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	38490610	0.0171	3.3135	0.0176	FASTmrEMMA
	20	27518350	-0.411	6.0768	0.0317	mrMLM			6	13614675	-0.0124	10.0289	3.476	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	20	27518350	-0.8764	5.5494	0.0362	FASTmrEMMA			7	2535953	-0.0044	2.0059	0.4032	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	20	27518350	-0.4319	5.103	5.0662	pLARmEB			7	6803101	-0.0112	8.3136	2.9629	ISIS EM-BLASSO
LH	3	6692444	-0.6908	4.7997	0.053	mrMLM			7	6439407	-0.0116	5.172	5.7288	pKWmEB
	3	46445726	0.7051	3.1781	0.046	mrMLM			7	35683968	-0.0071	3.3074	2.2218	pKWmEB
	4	43027190	-0.4049	3.0981	1.3884	ISIS EM-BLASSO			7	5602154	-0.0098	3.5113	4.2048	pKWmEB
	6	44099223	-0.59	4.2942	2.9481	ISIS EM-BLASSO			7	2535953	-0.0125	8.0124	0.0455	mrMLM
	6	44099223	-0.7701	3.0461	0.0475	mrMLM			7	6439407	-0.0303	9.6997	0.0554	FASTmrEMMA
	7	7640297	-0.5524	3.9961	3.612	pKWmEB			9	40777024	-0.0048	4.126	0.6225	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	7	7579727	-0.7495	5.0582	0.0673	mrMLM			9	40728456	1.69E-05	6.2998	1.18E-05	pKWmEB
	7	7579727	-1.2165	4.5657	0.0389	FASTmrEMMA			10	10187465	0.0105	7.7299	2.7781	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	7	7579727	-0.6600	5.0346	2.9667	pLARmEB			10	42589120	0.0082	8.2788	1.7159	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	8	46652014	0.9076	2.8325	0.021	FASTmrEMMA			10	44469282	0.0085	4.386	0.024	mrMLM
	9	36827262	-0.3917	3.0359	1.755	ISIS EM-BLASSO			10	44469282	0.0217	3.2101	0.0266	FASTmrEMMA
	9	27690827	0.488	3.9559	4.8124	pLARmEB			11	11121307	-0.0107	6.6888	1.9227	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	13	28444716	-0.4659	3.7133	2.7422	ISIS EM-BLASSO			11	36968274	-0.0035	3.1532	0.4581	pKWmEB
	13	28360967	0.5237	3.2754	2.4792	pKWmEB			11	8139744	-0.0112	4.241	5.5405	pKWmEB
	13	29046398	-1.7365	3.5193	0.0271	FASTmrEMMA			11	11013845	-0.01	3.2191	0.0364	mrMLM
	14	45238869	-0.4773	4.0376	2.635	ISIS EM-BLASSO			11	4035601	0.025	5.3613	0.0786	mrMLM
	14	45238869	-0.716	4.1493	0.0561	mrMLM			11	36968274	-0.011	6.9113	0.0401	mrMLM
	14	40390057	0.3779	2.006	3.7479	pLARmEB			11	10898421	-0.0248	4.0157	0.0389	FASTmrEMMA
	15	44193203	-0.6117	2.9667	4.0434	ISIS EM-BLASSO			12	38071047	8.86E-05	3.7302	1.00E-04	pKWmEB
	15	44193203	-0.8064	3.8477	7.3127	pKWmEB			13	6919676	0.0052	2.5092	0.7206	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	15	44193203	-1.3195	2.9789	0.0191	FASTmrEMMA			14	41609545	0	2.5823	0	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	16	28357655	0.5025	4.8124	3.2508	ISIS EM-BLASSO			14	29652207	0.0126	3.2387	0.0401	mrMLM

	16	29225627	-0.7389	3.7479	2.968	ISIS EM-BLASSO		15	4485355	0.0085	5.7496	1.5208	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	16	36234201	0.5119	4.7388	3.3019	ISIS EM-BLASSO		15	17148291	-0.0099	4.71	0.87	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	16	36234201	0.7103	3.7832	0.0601	mrMLM		15	36572861	-0.0424	8.7762	0.0584	mrMLM
	17	32387192	-0.6413	5.8622	5.2528	ISIS EM-BLASSO		16	30028848	-0.0097	8.61	1.8979	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	17	24783226	-0.6324	4.7801	4.7388	pLARmEB		16	29245699	-0.0275	3.4219	0.0744	mrMLM
	18	6705051	9.93E-02	5.18E-12	0.013	GEMMA		16	30210113	0.015	2.6381	0.0142	FASTmrEMMA
	19	21166248	1.1992	3.112	0.0245	FASTmrEMMA		17	8760885	0.0152	11.1708	5.1335	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	20	3607733	0.635	5.7528	5.2253	ISIS EM-BLASSO		17	8760885	0.0137	9.1062	6.7781	pKWmEB
	20	45734650	0.9729	3.4055	5.8622	pLARmEB		17	8760885	0.0099	4.1824	0.031	mrMLM
DWR	1	674489	0.0018	2.286	2.3809	ISIS EM-BLASSO		17	8760885	0.0222	4.3767	0.023	FASTmrEMMA
	1	54525183	-0.0016	4.2185	2.6311	ISIS EM-BLASSO		18	6705051	-0.0502	17.5196	9.482	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	2	49146815	-0.0031	4.2347	0.0965	mrMLM		18	58692570	0.0069	5.4209	0.9873	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	2	9955199	0.0029	2.8073	0.0198	FASTmrEMMA		18	6705051	-0.0448	11.291	0.1071	mrMLM
	2	49146815	-0.0047	3.3159	0.0484	FASTmrEMMA		19	36223338	0.0002	2.2609	0.0003	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	1218900	-0.0017	4.2386	2.5326	ISIS EM-BLASSO	DWR	12	3507002	-0.0148	3.7798	0.0889	mrMLM
	3	40571421	0.0017	4.5036	3.0321	ISIS EM-BLASSO		13	5200212	0.0011	3.036	1.0655	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	40571421	0.0026	2.8957	0.0176	FASTmrEMMA		13	40977541	0.0014	5.1247	2.1434	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	44194519	-0.0008	2.5069	0.5772	ISIS EM-BLASSO		14	49541759	-0.0008	2.5036	0.6734	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	40972027	-0.0015	3.432	1.6425	ISIS EM-BLASSO		15	4437819	0.002	3.6046	3.2057	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	6	40931811	0.002	5.0497	3.0455	ISIS EM-BLASSO		15	17391737	-0.0029	3.1482	0.0217	FASTmrEMMA
	7	7827587	-0.0024	3.2415	0.016	FASTmrEMMA		17	5878894	-0.0013	2.1244	1.3152	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	8	4836334	0	2.1859	0.0004	ISIS EM-BLASSO		18	55891781	-6.83E-05	251.1838	0.0053	pKWmEB
	9	40898778	-0.0018	4.2096	3.8545	ISIS EM-BLASSO		18	11156040	0.0028	3.7718	0.0222	FASTmrEMMA
	9	32402525	-4.00E-04	164.7804	0.2746	pKWmEB		20	41343	-0.0017	7.0636	3.4371	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	9	40898778	-0.0041	6.369	0.0439	FASTmrEMMA		20	41343	-0.0016	2.7985	0.0074	FASTmrEMMA

LR: main root length; LH: length of hypocotyls of healthy seedlings after treatments with control; FWR: the fresh weights of roots; DWR: dry weights of roots; BS: the biomass of seedlings.

Table S3. Significantly associated SNPs for five quantitative traits in soybean water treatment datasets in 2015 using six GWAS methods

Trait	Chr	Position (bp)	Genome-wide association studies				Trait Effect	Chr	Position (bp)	Genome-wide association studies			
			Effect	LOD	r ² (%)	Method				Effect	LOD	r ² (%)	Method
LR	1	469595	-0.4208	3.2051	1.2605	ISIS EM-BLASSO	DWR	1	48290180	0.0016	2.3818	1.9112	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	469595	-0.5326	3.5673	2.4704	pKWmEB		1	54525183	-0.0012	2.3929	1.3273	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	43964681	-0.9055	3.299	8.4313	pKWmEB		1	4575182	-0.0301	3.0055	9.183	pKWmEB
	1	469595	-0.5453	3.6212	2.0357	pLARmEB		1	6352689	0.0322	9.1943	0.0902	mrMLM
	3	550332	-0.3918	3.3174	0.8677	ISIS EM-BLASSO		3	17127049	-0.0025	4.38	3.3459	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	2345308	-0.6015	3.3732	2.2006	ISIS EM-BLASSO		3	37981151	-0.002	7.707	3.962	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	3036257	-0.5182	3.8861	1.1222	ISIS EM-BLASSO		3	35584835	-0.0127	3.0104	0.0384	mrMLM
	3	34977716	-0.2937	2.1731	0.7422	ISIS EM-BLASSO		4	36889243	0.0192	5.7973	0.0689	mrMLM
	3	34977716	-0.667	3.1046	0.0388	mrMLM		5	32614728	-0.0018	4.7733	2.0007	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	3	3036257	-1.0981	3.201	0.0135	FASTmrEMMA		5	20165315	-0.0526	7.7443	0.0919	mrMLM
	3	3036257	-0.0028	2.1064	1.3251	pLARmEB		5	38536365	0.0041	3.5804	0.0407	FASTmrEMMA
	3	34977716	-0.4886	2.8175	3.9726	pLARmEB		6	11824566	0.001	2.6611	1.0612	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	43886472	-0.8047	6.2148	3.4647	ISIS EM-BLASSO		6	50540634	1.26E-05	6.0826	1.54E-06	pKWmEB
	4	43886472	-0.7018	4.2256	3.2238	pKWmEB		7	27022334	0.0023	2.4222	3.9172	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	43886472	-1.0091	6.6416	0.0552	mrMLM		7	34796471	-0.0015	3.2403	2.0884	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	4	43886472	-0.6934	3.9145	3.4568	pLARmEB		7	19338710	-0.0529	12.5733	0.1042	mrMLM
	5	27252986	-0.4553	4.2778	1.7611	ISIS EM-BLASSO		7	5084965	-0.0212	6.2819	0.0513	mrMLM
	5	28840522	-0.6465	4.4942	2.0357	ISIS EM-BLASSO		9	2858744	0.0016	4.3669	2.814	ISIS EM-BLASSO

	5	771731	1.37E-07	7.69E-02	0.016	GEMMA			9	33271673	0.002	6.0508	4.23	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	27252986	-0.4375	3.8158	5.3463	pLARmEB			9	3532214	0.0039	3.3818	0.0263	FASTmrEMMA
	6	44099223	-0.4907	3.426	1.3251	ISIS EM-BLASSO			10	48823212	-3.00E-04	4.7128	0.0015	pKWmEB
	7	5604359	0.7144	4.3661	3.9726	ISIS EM-BLASSO			11	922322	0.0213	4.3266	0.0579	mrMLM
	7	8579088	-3.7403	4.3886	3.4568	ISIS EM-BLASSO			13	24027256	0.0005	1.7727	0.2737	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	7	5604359	0.2891	2.2689	1.4356	pLARmEB			14	30115761	5.80E-05	3.3772	7.45E-05	pKWmEB
	7	8579088	-3.6417	3.3143	3.1729	pLARmEB			14	29652207	0.0044	2.8573	0.0282	FASTmrEMMA
	8	1819411	0.7863	9.4554	5.3463	ISIS EM-BLASSO			15	47621157	0.0113	5.7769	0.0385	mrMLM
	8	1819411	0.6622	6.0621	4.6388	pKWmEB			17	4980483	0.0005	2.0871	0.0828	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	8	1819411	0.8974	7.4854	0.0705	mrMLM			17	8592762	0.0017	2.9091	1.4953	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	8	1819411	0.7347	6.5621	3.1891	pLARmEB			17	15179679	0.0032	4.2885	2.0598	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	10	5470637	-0.4562	3.8098	1.4356	ISIS EM-BLASSO			18	4500377	0.0013	3.9431	1.6956	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	10	5470637	-0.6777	3.1636	0.0321	mrMLM			18	60579752	-0.0192	5.7299	0.0471	mrMLM
	11	270458	0.71	4.123	0.0331	mrMLM			19	47406415	-0.001	2.5006	0.8424	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	12	3224174	0.69	5.8733	3.1729	ISIS EM-BLASSO			20	36230715	-0.0149	5.2338	0.0528	mrMLM
	12	3224174	0.9635	5.5285	0.0626	mrMLM			20	290334	-0.0035	3.5033	0.0268	FASTmrEMMA
	13	11425980	0.6041	3.0427	3.1891	ISIS EM-BLASSO		BS	1	4575182	-0.0142	2.8013	1.9577	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	13	20704034	1.77E-08	1.08E-01	0.011	GEMMA			1	6458540	0.0233	8.4597	4.0058	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	13	11425980	0.9436	4.1298	0.0788	mrMLM			1	48290180	0.0066	2.2902	0.7845	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	15	21875502	-0.6783	5.1015	2.9803	ISIS EM-BLASSO			1	55375068	-0.0063	2.5681	0.4775	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	15	21875502	-0.7612	3.3512	0.038	mrMLM			1	4575182	-0.0301	3.0055	9.183	pKWmEB

	15	21875502	-0.7959	6.0719	2.9803	pLARmEB			1	6352689	0.0322	9.1943	0.0902	mrMLM
	16	753988	1.4099	11.0353	9.6813	ISIS EM-BLASSO			1	55375068	-0.0293	4.9128	0.0276	FASTmrEMMA
	16	986439	-0.8945	4.9412	3.4532	pKWmEB			1	3798182	0.0019	6.0934	2.9803	pLARmEB
	16	753988	1.5478	9.039	0.1181	mrMLM			1	47076288	0.0012	3.3181	9.6813	pLARmEB
	16	986439	-1.8665	4.6979	0.0317	FASTmrEMMA			2	50826684	-0.0091	3.5142	1.6978	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	16	753988	1.1813	5.5728	9.6813	pLARmEB			2	49058778	-0.0162	2.8717	0.011	FASTmrEMMA
	17	1301404	0.4446	2.7621	1.3049	ISIS EM-BLASSO			2	39904103	-0.0012	3.0247	1.3049	pLARmEB
	17	1301404	1.6231	3.9577	0.0297	FASTmrEMMA			2	50853970	-0.0011	5.0691	0.011	pLARmEB
	19	45826860	0.9401	3.0136	0.0169	FASTmrEMMA			3	35584835	-0.0127	3.0104	0.0384	mrMLM
	20	33662021	1.4748	4.7384	0.0429	FASTmrEMMA			3	28770900	0.0023	3.6938	0.016	pLARmEB
LH	1	4000809	-0.6654	4.0542	0.0281	FASTmrEMMA			4	9631962	-0.0097	5.3959	2.5057	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	2	14398729	-0.4876	4.1119	1.9715	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	36889243	0.0192	5.7973	0.0689	mrMLM
	2	44227083	-0.3539	3.5965	2.0387	ISIS EM-BLASSO			4	8176842	0.001	5.1386	4.6388	pLARmEB
	2	11503697	0.4837	6.2592	0.0586	mrMLM			4	15940426	0.0016	4.736	2.4704	pLARmEB
	2	14398729	-0.8953	3.1625	0.0182	FASTmrEMMA			5	20165315	-0.0526	7.7443	0.0919	mrMLM
	2	11503697	0.5078	5.0711	0.0317	pLARmEB			5	31575389	0.0694	4.3874	0.0247	FASTmrEMMA
	3	37430261	1.2963	10.2481	10.3682	ISIS EM-BLASSO			5	31668886	0.0017	5.3611	3.2238	pLARmEB
	3	37430261	0.5699	3.252	0.0297	pLARmEB			5	35470350	-0.0014	2.9501	3.4532	pLARmEB
	6	38573353	-0.3954	5.6894	4.1875	ISIS EM-BLASSO			6	47610510	-0.0406	3.3601	2.587	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	6	38573353	-0.604	3.0219	0.0192	FASTmrEMMA			6	50540634	1.26E-05	6.0826	1.54E-06	pKWmEB
	8	7909117	-0.6779	3.9981	0.0633	mrMLM			6	47610510	-0.0235	2.991	8.4313	pLARmEB

	10	7178841	-0.4331	2.9811	0.8108	ISIS EM-BLASSO			6	49465946	-0.0015	2.9686	0.0705	pLARmEB
	10	7178841	-0.6094	3.6272	0.0169	pLARmEB			7	5084965	-0.0152	4.3136	2.4572	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	10	46108165	0.4379	3.5909	0.0429	pLARmEB			7	19338710	-0.0327	6.3008	3.7025	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	10	50920719	0.0014	2.0421	2.0357	pLARmEB			7	19338710	-0.0529	12.5733	0.1042	mrMLM
	13	27024688	-0.3487	4.6953	2.8238	ISIS EM-BLASSO			7	5084965	-0.0212	6.2819	0.0513	mrMLM
	13	27024688	-0.8096	4.8344	0.0312	FASTmrEMMA			7	6463019	-0.0186	3.6113	0.0219	FASTmrEMMA
	14	80776	0.4715	3.7768	5.5276	ISIS EM-BLASSO			7	1292425	0.0025	3.4082	2.3809	pLARmEB
	14	80776	0.3286	2.5761	1.3251	pLARmEB			7	6803101	-0.0027	4.4465	2.6311	pLARmEB
	15	15597899	0.3802	4.7627	3.0762	ISIS EM-BLASSO			7	6944855	-0.001	2.6614	2.5326	pLARmEB
	15	48997377	-0.2047	3.0722	1.4649	pKWmEB			8	6978949	-0.0086	2.0955	0.6046	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	15	18118976	-0.7818	3.9265	0.1759	mrMLM			8	43127956	-0.0087	2.5401	1.0559	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	15	15597899	0.8378	5.0481	0.0314	FASTmrEMMA			8	10901338	-0.001	3.6647	3.0321	pLARmEB
	16	31510375	0.6479	4.6005	0.0751	mrMLM			8	13564732	0.0024	2.8836	0.5772	pLARmEB
	16	5422259	-0.2236	3.7766	3.9726	pLARmEB			8	17248047	0.0012	2.4316	1.6425	pLARmEB
	17	16112138	-0.6832	4.4059	6.2722	ISIS EM-BLASSO			8	35014518	0.0012	2.0629	3.0455	pLARmEB
	17	5037006	-0.4773	2.7576	0.0149	FASTmrEMMA			8	43523091	-0.0013	2.5784	0.0004	pLARmEB
	17	33844338	-0.0748	2.1883	3.4568	pLARmEB			9	33440599	0.006	3.2723	0.8833	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	18	60092421	0.3256	2.6053	0.7304	ISIS EM-BLASSO			9	3532214	0.0026	6.0349	3.8545	pLARmEB
	18	62264999	0.8192	3.765	5.3571	pKWmEB			9	7031683	-0.0014	2.4461	1.0655	pLARmEB
	19	37732107	-0.5599	5.113	3.0238	ISIS EM-BLASSO			9	7981195	0.0019	2.7025	2.1434	pLARmEB
	19	37732107	-0.6462	3.2058	0.0422	mrMLM			9	38945031	0.0027	2.0734	0.6734	pLARmEB

	19	40372478	-0.2318	5.038	5.3463	pLARmEB			10	48823212	-3.00E-04	4.7128	0.0015	pKWmEB
	20	27518350	-0.2447	3.4114	1.2368	ISIS EM-BLASSO			10	42750933	0.025	3.9142	0.0273	FASTmrEMMA
	20	1321742	-0.2778	3.1971	2.3729	pKWmEB			10	47129404	0.0012	5.5528	3.2057	pLARmEB
	20	1321742	-0.5585	6.4536	0.0822	mrMLM			11	922322	0.0133	3.9613	2.1068	ISIS EM-BLASSO
FWR	1	51528827	0.0535	6.3208	4.695	ISIS EM-BLASSO			11	10898421	-0.0082	3.296	1.8733	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	53721534	0.0001	1.9417	0	ISIS EM-BLASSO			11	29889627	0.0061	2.8137	0.9666	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	1	4442760	0.0244	4.3192	2.876	pKWmEB			11	922322	0.0213	4.3266	0.0579	mrMLM
	1	6352689	0.0322	9.1943	0.0902	mrMLM			11	8085669	-0.029	6.7801	0.0502	FASTmrEMMA
	3	35584835	-0.0127	3.0104	0.0384	mrMLM			11	28841785	-0.0011	5.1692	1.3152	pLARmEB
	3	28794038	0.0027	2.9342	3.9726	pLARmEB			12	34894949	-0.015	2.7046	0.0123	FASTmrEMMA
	4	36044496	0.0343	6.3393	4.1674	ISIS EM-BLASSO			12	26059845	-0.0112	5.4412	3.4371	pLARmEB
	4	36889243	0.0192	5.7973	0.0689	mrMLM			13	43566149	0.0013	7.0849	0.0579	pLARmEB
	4	38378773	0.0493	2.6354	0.0272	FASTmrEMMA			14	40566564	0.0057	2.0441	0.6239	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	5	38490610	0.0219	4.3076	2.5856	ISIS EM-BLASSO			14	30115761	5.80E-05	3.3772	7.45E-05	pKWmEB
	5	20165315	-0.0526	7.7443	0.0919	mrMLM			14	42664947	-0.0017	2.6371	0.0385	pLARmEB
	5	39314883	0.0204	3.1408	3.4568	pLARmEB			14	44689162	0.0026	2.1408	0.0902	pLARmEB
	6	11096433	-0.0072	2.1278	5.3463	pLARmEB			14	46610521	-0.0014	2.4542	0.0528	pLARmEB
	6	49995853	0.0082	2.7484	4.695	pLARmEB			14	47079327	-0.0034	6.0543	0.0384	pLARmEB
	7	19338710	-0.0529	12.5733	0.1042	mrMLM			15	47621157	0.0113	5.7769	0.0385	mrMLM
	7	5084965	-0.0212	6.2819	0.0513	mrMLM			15	7023132	-0.0021	3.308	0.0689	pLARmEB
	7	4079231	0.0095	3.7195	0	pLARmEB			15	50368720	-0.0022	2.5523	0.0407	pLARmEB

	8	39363005	-0.0176	3.805	1.1676	ISIS EM-BLASSO			16	31480258	-0.0289	5.839	5.6	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	8	39363005	-0.0213	3.5559	2.0823	pKWmEB			16	29752721	-0.0028	7.111	0.0263	pLARmEB
	8	39363005	-0.0117	2.0865	4.1674	pLARmEB			16	31550275	0.0011	3.2154	0.0282	pLARmEB
	9	3532214	0.0301	5.2841	3.5254	ISIS EM-BLASSO			16	32944622	-0.0032	2.2077	0.071	pLARmEB
	9	3532214	0.0215	3.4032	2.1988	pKWmEB			17	1752486	0.0054	2.6502	0.5121	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	9	3532214	0.0641	4.7465	0.0349	FASTmrEMMA			17	4450019	0.0016	2.8168	0.0644	pLARmEB
	9	3532214	0.0095	3.6638	2.5856	pLARmEB			17	6264102	-0.0056	2.5904	0.1356	pLARmEB
	11	8247884	-0.0232	4.9728	3.2464	pKWmEB			17	40687790	0.0014	5.2675	0.048	pLARmEB
	11	922322	0.0213	4.3266	0.0579	mrMLM			18	60579752	-0.0139	4.3838	2.3053	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	12	8419886	-0.0026	2.4791	1.1676	pLARmEB			18	60579752	-0.0192	5.7299	0.0471	mrMLM
	13	11667005	-0.021	3.5916	2.012	ISIS EM-BLASSO			18	2103018	0.0019	2.9214	0.0317	pLARmEB
	14	8383046	0.0218	3.166	1.7017	ISIS EM-BLASSO			18	54943988	-0.0014	2.1261	0.0351	pLARmEB
	14	8383046	0.0373	5.8075	6.0979	pKWmEB			18	60452547	-0.001	3.6791	0.0253	pLARmEB
	14	29652207	0	2.5441	0	FASTmrEMMA			18	60579752	-0.0042	2.2019	0.0663	pLARmEB
	14	8383046	0.0023	2.2919	3.5254	pLARmEB			19	36243807	0.0014	3.9871	0.0448	pLARmEB
	15	42714810	-0.0244	2.5803	2.9719	ISIS EM-BLASSO			19	45452972	-0.0014	11.616	0.0208	pLARmEB
	15	47621157	0.0113	5.7769	0.0385	mrMLM			20	36230715	-0.0149	5.2338	0.0528	mrMLM
	15	4485355	0.0357	2.7473	0.0119	FASTmrEMMA		FWR	18	56748069	0	2.3928	0	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	15	21875502	-0.0031	2.1334	2.012	pLARmEB			18	60579752	-0.0192	5.7299	0.0471	mrMLM
	16	753988	0.0331	3.5223	3.342	ISIS EM-BLASSO			19	36243807	0.0298	3.8086	2.5169	ISIS EM-BLASSO
	16	753988	0.0324	4.4263	3.9054	pKWmEB			19	5135732	0.0065	3.7537	0.0902	pLARmEB

	16	36773852	-0.0134	2.8234	1.7017	pLARmEB			20	36230715	-0.0149	5.2338	0.0528	mrMLM
	17	40455828	-0.0337	3.9483	0.0135	FASTmrEMMA			20	40884346	-0.0214	3.8439	0.0528	pLARmEB

LR: main root length; LH: length of hypocotyls of healthy seedlings after treatments with control; FWR: the fresh weights of roots; DWR: dry weights of roots; BS: the biomass of seedlings.

Table S4. Significantly associated SNPs for five quantitative traits in Soybean datasets with salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014 using six GWAS methods

Trait	Chr	Position (bp)	Genome-wide association studies				Trait	Chr	Position (bp)	Genome-wide association studies			
			Effect	LOD	r ² (%)	Method				Effect	LOD	r ² (%)	Method
LR	1	55739787	-0.534241269	4.143927639	0.047548336	FASTmrEMMA	LH	1	3851548	0.168845	3.423597	1.935446	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	1	55739787	-0.232833609	4.423464172	3.4294	pLARmEB		1	905392	0.364777	5.791098	0.078186	mrMLM
	2	10509909	0.208914288	4.383217783	2.455197819	ISIS-EMBLASSO		2	47371322	0.423773	3.047573	0.030738	FASTmrEMMA
	2	5973085	0.586534974	3.290630217	0.113312534	mrMLM		3	34969942	-0.33484	7.417835	5.995321	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	2	5973085	0.226255824	3.197255693	1.8682	pLARmEB		3	45302035	0.24259	5.302101	3.368964	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	3	45092604	0.216534188	4.423983554	2.951275285	ISIS-EMBLASSO		3	37035164	-0.51162	3.95925	0.036895	FASTmrEMMA
	3	45119353	0.0555	3.5252	0.1443	pKWmEB		4	42944392	-0.37996	5.337048	0.086908	mrMLM
	3	45119353	0.278927252	5.726943845	4.0754	pLARmEB		6	48796733	-0.2022	4.261215	2.919858	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	5	40423773	-0.336604303	4.16326596	5.021678903	ISIS-EMBLASSO		6	48809715	-0.2389	3.5105	4.3549	pKWmEB
	5	40423773	-0.3617	3.9334	4.9008	pKWmEB		7	38165084	0.2397	3.3057	3.9805	pKWmEB
	5	40423773	-0.43776633	4.419048362	0.072403661	mrMLM		7	38165084	0.473452	4.392162	0.035978	FASTmrEMMA
	5	31519265	-0.143938812	3.883768961	1.4485	pLARmEB		9	46357159	0.234641	4.902557	3.035654	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	5	40423773	-0.35592161	4.955769962	5.3029	pLARmEB		10	49165057	-0.33016	7.043776	4.879714	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	6	45746480	0.28733817	4.762526865	0.062546729	mrMLM		10	39066086	0.276181	4.535926	0.044709	mrMLM
9	8855062	-0.087092214	2.523688527	0.666033153	ISIS-EMBLASSO	10	49165057	-0.54605	8.258693	0.108972	mrMLM		
11	2039409	0.200828164	5.262035922	3.445240427	ISIS-EMBLASSO	10	46435147	-0.51917	3.235535	0.031609	FASTmrEMMA		
11	15528496	-0.132247319	2.644927698	1.401225001	ISIS-EMBLASSO	11	922317	-2.22E-05	2.172115	1.58E-08	ISIS-EMBLASSO		
11	15528496	-0.2521	4.6173	4.3035	pKWmEB	13	39657178	-0.1772	4.02329	2.316653	ISIS-EMBLASSO		
11	15528496	-0.326844725	5.411333788	0.072959741	mrMLM	13	40961262	-0.14641	2.957418	1.583276	ISIS-EMBLASSO		
11	5245829	-0.175009276	3.592977289	2.2935	pLARmEB	14	29101337	-0.23208	3.082627	4.0132	pLARmEB		
11	15528496	-0.242191385	4.772730004	4.4386	pLARmEB	14	33945380	0.142791	2.999542	1.1674	pLARmEB		
11	16176922	0.184323867	4.145384306	2.8335	pLARmEB	14	44936364	0.001164	2.718096	0	pLARmEB		
14	8727726	0.137112547	3.351943241	1.506220374	ISIS-EMBLASSO	14	33945380	0.316632	5.677632	5.360881	ISIS-EMBLASSO		

	16	28088	-0.228097462	5.535413954	4.621761211	ISIS-EMBLASSO		14	44936364	0.507684	8.739152	7.426182	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	16	4294458	0.268308641	3.086014155	3.575162307	ISIS-EMBLASSO		14	29101337	-0.40399	7.335034	0.092729	mrMLM
	16	4296878	0.2725	4.3211	4.5773	pKWmEB		14	1109591	0.46928	3.14997	0.021088	FASTmrEMMA
	16	4296878	0.333112298	3.685487678	0.068999033	mrMLM		14	29101337	-0.50557	4.415215	0.03939	FASTmrEMMA
	16	4296878	0.67772536	5.387597983	0.067222382	FASTmrEMMA		15	47403591	0.149066	3.361434	1.7568	pLARmEB
	16	28144	-0.2413	5.5129	4.3688	pKWmEB		15	14962700	-0.25469	5.315306	4.047578	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	17	4008933	-0.222957724	3.74441334	2.985858904	ISIS-EMBLASSO		16	27402947	0.191477	4.062804	2.416341	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	17	4321129	-0.261512616	7.736216821	5.681299351	ISIS-EMBLASSO		16	424243	-0.51847	3.242787	0.028237	FASTmrEMMA
	17	5966671	-0.2845	3.5568	4.1602	pKWmEB		17	4008933	-0.15513	2.624677	1.3652	pLARmEB
	18	1690520	0.218875806	3.995889062	3.239347114	ISIS-EMBLASSO		17	39188268	-0.23086	2.385518	3.2074	pLARmEB
	18	11958740	-0.266576776	7.379213702	5.088808818	ISIS-EMBLASSO		17	12543455	0.232691	5.189314	3.0146	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	20	35084084	-0.423198539	5.423457768	14.81799898	ISIS-EMBLASSO		17	41448838	0.500966	5.107199	4.315842	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	20	35084084	-2.32E-05	3.1317	3.76E-08	pKWmEB		17	33217750	-0.24921	3.252452	0.037068	mrMLM
DWR	2	6170248	0.001212	6.475239	3.939902	ISIS-EMBLASSO		18	7155745	0.228609	2.645379	2.9922	pLARmEB
	2	6170248	0.001789	3.27949	0.019794	FASTmrEMMA		18	11958740	-0.17262	3.839148	2.2846	pLARmEB
	3	45347726	3.00E-04	38.9655	0.1961	pKWmEB		18	7155745	0.227465	3.747298	2.766663	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	4	4563211	8.01E-05	2.631161	0.015977	ISIS-EMBLASSO	FWR	1	49320983	-0.01663	3.598983	0.033846	mrMLM
	4	44684592	1.10E-07	8.23E-03	0.011	GEMMA		1	49320983	-0.01817	2.666417	0.010198	FASTmrEMMA
	4	44684592	-0.00521	3.588563	0.123347	mrMLM		1	588851	-0.00462	4.004895	1.2924	pLARmEB
	4	11471448	-0.00393	3.415895	0.096853	mrMLM		1	3127993	-0.00116	3.050409	0.056	pLARmEB
	5	38536365	0.002685	4.340091	0.045581	FASTmrEMMA		1	4309825	-0.0013	4.825785	0.1261	pLARmEB
	6	48796733	-0.00138	2.955669	0.011052	FASTmrEMMA		1	4325636	0.001946	15.46581	0.2894	pLARmEB
	7	8154426	0.000654	2.492561	1.203749	ISIS-EMBLASSO		1	5760920	0.001367	2.804398	0.0392	pLARmEB
	7	8579088	-0.00102	2.598267	0.135	pLARmEB		1	6178120	0.001251	4.905636	0.0528	pLARmEB
	8	12613030	-0.00097	4.966773	1.856427	ISIS-EMBLASSO		1	31859699	-0.00105	5.166391	0.02	pLARmEB
	8	18372849	0.000643	3.309302	1.094115	ISIS-EMBLASSO		1	54142479	-0.00285	4.216971	0.4645	pLARmEB
	9	43496689	5.10E-05	2.749988	0.007405	ISIS-EMBLASSO		1	55694820	-0.00151	4.072202	0.1345	pLARmEB

	9	46559895	-0.002	3.183608	3.376882	ISIS-EMBLASSO		2	1443753	0.001728	2.18695	0.1271	pLARmEB
	10	3948695	-0.00105	4.575875	2.227416	ISIS-EMBLASSO		2	12668957	0.001303	6.318462	0.0696	pLARmEB
	10	7381663	-0.00168	5.626063	4.507493	ISIS-EMBLASSO		2	44943084	0.001185	2.270833	0.0698	pLARmEB
	10	46596686	-9.71E-05	2.415947	0.016806	ISIS-EMBLASSO		3	35235318	-0.01422	4.794561	4.250205	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	10	7381663	-0.00172	3.295046	0.053327	mrMLM		3	35233981	-0.02777	3.443904	0.030786	FASTmrEMMA
	10	11114618	0.002261	2.676132	0.014424	FASTmrEMMA		3	590515	0.001173	7.108939	0.0684	pLARmEB
	10	3948695	-0.00236	3.75575	0.027993	FASTmrEMMA		3	41439576	0.001127	5.754858	0.0978	pLARmEB
	11	1399197	-0.0019	3.686381	6.428758	ISIS-EMBLASSO		3	44000516	-0.00172	4.254709	0.1305	pLARmEB
	11	11160583	-0.001	3.065597	2.290738	ISIS-EMBLASSO		3	45380341	-0.00379	3.999879	1.0423	pLARmEB
	14	7504616	0.00098	2.781803	2.643592	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	44273143	-0.01247	4.210004	0.04306	mrMLM
	14	46893280	-0.00077	2.813281	1.689678	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	5030664	0.00128	4.260862	0.0538	pLARmEB
	14	46971839	-0.00165	2.939995	0.017011	FASTmrEMMA		4	10166745	0.001489	10.97868	0.0528	pLARmEB
	16	35773373	-0.00017	2.673733	0.061882	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	12771897	-0.00104	7.509612	0.0562	pLARmEB
	17	5878894	-0.00104	2.314312	1.869465	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	15272659	0.002013	20.1325	0.3123	pLARmEB
	18	60224658	0.00048	2.021498	0.02857	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	15781563	0.00112	2.362938	0.0379	pLARmEB
	19	39194792	0.000737	3.969699	1.148109	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	29515674	-0.00141	4.110075	0.1149	pLARmEB
BS	1	51353516	0.002069	2.40513	0.2521	pLARmEB		4	44348434	0.001877	2.640931	0.0671	pLARmEB
	2	13638052	-0.00649	2.589382	0.767479	ISIS-EMBLASSO		5	38425844	0.019641	9.764037	9.778301	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	2	13638052	-0.01735	5.864109	0.061664	mrMLM		5	38490610	0.016191	6.848786	0.072898	mrMLM
	3	5480371	-0.00664	2.665455	0.965149	ISIS-EMBLASSO		5	38490610	0.039082	8.514467	0.088296	FASTmrEMMA
	3	29644613	0.005327	2.197256	0.708306	ISIS-EMBLASSO		5	2994169	-0.00169	3.619692	0.2158	pLARmEB
	3	29644613	0.0117	4.9505	6.2235	pKWmEB		5	38490643	-0.00475	2.939032	1.734	pLARmEB
	3	4902255	0.005712	5.395832	1.5433	pLARmEB		5	38574145	0.002396	2.475006	0.442	pLARmEB
	3	19457811	0.001478	3.15708	0.0848	pLARmEB		6	2934819	-0.00363	10.28303	1.0178	pLARmEB
	3	29000124	0.002639	2.961862	0.5584	pLARmEB		6	10259975	0.001387	2.126233	0.0862	pLARmEB
	3	29644613	0.005721	3.313989	2.7751	pLARmEB		6	50139547	0.001876	4.206417	0.2612	pLARmEB
	3	31077361	0.001885	4.204689	0.1091	pLARmEB		7	5516242	-0.00134	7.790316	0.0443	pLARmEB

4	36931911	0.012414	4.707029	2.265327	ISIS-EMBLASSO		7	8579088	-0.00284	9.341074	0.0181	pLARmEB
4	37908695	0.0105	3.2505	4.4868	pKWmEB		7	43668786	0.002123	5.646417	0.2084	pLARmEB
4	37908695	0.015797	8.691865	0.06277	mrMLM		8	7981098	0.002508	2.222118	0.4172	pLARmEB
4	4924161	-0.03103	4.445477	0.025919	FASTmrEMMA		8	10481382	0.002088	4.334441	0.1984	pLARmEB
4	36767989	0.026788	3.623056	0.030258	FASTmrEMMA		8	12259502	-0.00241	4.524342	0.3699	pLARmEB
4	2474142	0.00121	3.794033	0.0718	pLARmEB		8	14221685	0.002149	2.637357	0.3288	pLARmEB
4	7437421	-0.00195	3.117147	0.3269	pLARmEB		8	16491223	-0.00177	2.951427	0.2253	pLARmEB
4	44314010	0.005016	3.566794	2.185	pLARmEB		8	46018286	-0.00173	6.914788	0.2237	pLARmEB
5	30060880	0.013986	3.21422	2.06519	ISIS-EMBLASSO		9	2282229	-0.0093	11.35991	2.6876	pLARmEB
5	38166911	0.00669	2.677002	1.055802	ISIS-EMBLASSO		9	10751617	-0.00364	4.018209	1.0051	pLARmEB
5	30060880	0.023329	3.961296	0.064614	mrMLM		9	42401888	0.002947	13.27963	0.3561	pLARmEB
5	38490610	0.024214	5.995015	0.034269	FASTmrEMMA		9	46357159	0.003869	2.167856	0.8658	pLARmEB
5	26834350	-0.00423	5.154447	1.3098	pLARmEB		10	4490676	0.019837	5.966946	4.783507	ISIS-EMBLASSO
5	33840764	-0.00116	2.955951	0.0766	pLARmEB		10	1346267	0.001005	6.099883	0.0182	pLARmEB
5	37001447	0.002267	2.119052	0.3652	pLARmEB		10	1646415	-0.00116	4.111149	0.0786	pLARmEB
5	40055670	-0.00101	3.021597	0.0478	pLARmEB		10	3166086	-0.00114	8.488643	0.0498	pLARmEB
6	14090512	0.010414	4.26934	0.031742	mrMLM		10	40887755	0.001269	9.636976	0.0486	pLARmEB
6	14090512	0.018896	3.888742	0.020816	FASTmrEMMA		10	42266387	0.00108	2.93769	0.0256	pLARmEB
6	1310389	-0.00498	3.999625	2.1686	pLARmEB		10	42750933	0.001675	4.920768	0.1836	pLARmEB
6	3564774	0.001938	2.387391	0.311	pLARmEB		11	30786330	0.019497	3.739619	4.725714	ISIS-EMBLASSO
6	47243084	0.001939	3.562745	0.2243	pLARmEB		11	35955645	-0.00749	3.050468	1.45385	ISIS-EMBLASSO
7	8154426	0.011916	7.980278	3.678061	ISIS-EMBLASSO		11	11316463	-0.01276	3.13302	0.039983	mrMLM
7	6439407	-0.0097	3.993	4.347	pKWmEB		11	11260323	0.001054	5.058145	0.0861	pLARmEB
7	2535953	-0.0074	3.4743	2.022	pKWmEB		11	11316463	-0.00114	4.990957	0.0876	pLARmEB
7	40338205	-0.007	5.1037	2.189	pKWmEB		11	12792598	-0.00106	2.153306	0.0858	pLARmEB
7	8154426	0.013242	6.920691	0.051071	mrMLM		11	30786330	0.002368	2.041014	0.2076	pLARmEB
7	8154426	0.020404	4.008357	0.024178	FASTmrEMMA		12	9384687	-0.00114	4.871108	0.0101	pLARmEB

7	5602154	-0.0035	2.172737	1.085	pLARmEB		12	38298460	0.001281	4.908843	0.1174	pLARmEB
7	6439407	-0.00107	3.623533	0.0994	pLARmEB		13	31992734	0.011499	4.861486	3.175909	ISIS-EMBLASSO
8	10415948	0.006093	2.993699	0.763436	ISIS-EMBLASSO		13	38837699	0.018591	3.534889	4.29689	ISIS-EMBLASSO
8	10415948	0.0055	4.0499	1.1429	pKWmEB		13	31992734	0.0103	10.1378	3.2137	pKWmEB
8	4710717	-0.0057	8.397418	2.1034	pLARmEB		13	26731110	0.015616	4.571983	0.061233	mrMLM
8	10314889	-0.00129	4.045353	0.1036	pLARmEB		13	31992734	0.015179	5.674723	0.059861	mrMLM
8	10901338	-0.002	2.012857	0.3378	pLARmEB		13	31992734	0.023475	4.162085	0.029271	FASTmrEMMA
8	14271249	0.002705	2.269648	0.5801	pLARmEB		13	7785678	-0.00295	2.745462	0.673	pLARmEB
9	49846	-0.01087	5.767364	0.033157	mrMLM		14	46971839	-0.00519	2.188956	0.63586	ISIS-EMBLASSO
9	334242	-0.01436	3.379554	0.012415	FASTmrEMMA		14	46971839	-0.01861	3.0711	0.019746	FASTmrEMMA
9	5992281	0.001915	2.354479	0.3064	pLARmEB		14	766808	0.001251	9.865226	0.0605	pLARmEB
9	37530389	0.003048	3.912603	0.6709	pLARmEB		14	2318704	-0.00138	2.498605	0.1302	pLARmEB
10	2562049	0.006729	3.98765	1.151462	ISIS-EMBLASSO		14	2397294	-0.00154	5.777899	0.1678	pLARmEB
10	10187465	0.013148	7.14777	4.216076	ISIS-EMBLASSO		14	2822924	0.001091	3.580896	0.0638	pLARmEB
10	44349907	-0.02105	4.873643	2.413273	ISIS-EMBLASSO		14	3264763	-0.00148	3.40269	0.1162	pLARmEB
10	10187465	0.0073	5.3901	2.3411	pKWmEB		14	46303978	0.001331	2.355509	0.0582	pLARmEB
10	44469282	0.0117	4.0613	5.4617	pKWmEB		15	575628	0.001039	3.046895	0.0326	pLARmEB
10	44672512	0.010421	4.360167	0.022494	mrMLM		15	14962700	-0.00221	4.985024	0.3208	pLARmEB
10	10187465	0.022321	4.081771	0.028882	FASTmrEMMA		15	15615693	0.002171	6.76342	0.2725	pLARmEB
10	3437511	-0.00437	3.484252	1.6903	pLARmEB		15	50190578	0.001387	6.922968	0.1258	pLARmEB
10	4357337	0.00191	4.572387	0.1453	pLARmEB		16	4888134	-0.02099	4.967287	0.060541	mrMLM
10	12464524	-0.00109	5.67288	0.0458	pLARmEB		16	4888134	-0.00298	6.119155	0.3354	pLARmEB
11	8139744	-0.00795	3.235336	0.018632	mrMLM		16	5986748	-0.00646	5.325358	3.0953	pLARmEB
11	8139744	-0.01929	5.233173	0.022412	FASTmrEMMA		16	11662038	0.001618	3.707515	0.1758	pLARmEB
12	7311683	-0.00872	6.514093	1.89606	ISIS-EMBLASSO		16	18847750	-0.00189	4.917248	0.2337	pLARmEB
12	7311683	-0.01116	5.448715	0.034975	mrMLM		16	29419215	0.001516	3.46897	0.0526	pLARmEB
12	5397244	-0.01859	6.997856	0.046686	mrMLM		16	29752721	-0.00125	2.26788	0.0553	pLARmEB

	12	19840149	0.004303	3.638921	1.3585	pLARmEB		16	32495843	-0.00118	6.068105	0.0608	pLARmEB
	12	20106666	0.002821	3.738538	0.4748	pLARmEB		16	34671131	-0.00259	5.640985	0.1658	pLARmEB
	13	32382549	-0.00679	3.15308	1.199727	ISIS-EMBLASSO		17	39188268	-0.0081	5.5295	1.662	pKWmEB
	13	28360967	-0.00179	3.360674	0.1844	pLARmEB		17	3396743	-0.0012	4.003139	0.0573	pLARmEB
	13	28892067	-0.00227	2.169107	0.0893	pLARmEB		17	5878894	-0.00176	8.894568	0.1452	pLARmEB
	13	43025008	-0.00151	2.852632	0.0603	pLARmEB		17	14829323	0.001009	6.265778	0.0262	pLARmEB
	14	46844001	-0.01081	4.854055	0.02654	mrMLM		18	60816379	-0.02024	2.968568	0.019908	FASTmrEMMA
	14	46844001	-0.0147	3.724814	0.01084	FASTmrEMMA		18	57453839	-0.00146	8.824057	0.1493	pLARmEB
	14	6326293	0.001998	2.233374	0.1432	pLARmEB		18	61747955	0.001098	2.62216	0.0932	pLARmEB
	14	44724955	0.002148	4.398256	0.408	pLARmEB		18	60816379	-0.01305	4.971122	4.205389	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	15	15793353	0.015704	4.217872	0.059874	mrMLM		19	40252738	-0.00112	5.967198	0.0954	pLARmEB
	15	15793353	0.010772	13.56414	8.5116	pLARmEB		19	45439353	0.002429	3.667682	0.1731	pLARmEB
	16	1867597	0.00528	2.993938	0.495567	ISIS-EMBLASSO		20	23995652	-0.08275	4.134285	0.138124	mrMLM
	16	3353180	-0.01718	6.884265	2.293808	ISIS-EMBLASSO		20	937215	-0.00284	4.708493	0.616	pLARmEB
	16	1500551	-0.0052	3.3635	1.1922	pKWmEB		20	4631858	0.001178	2.094763	0.0491	pLARmEB
	16	3353180	-0.01552	3.097968	0.021049	mrMLM		20	30383187	-0.00178	7.089733	0.1994	pLARmEB
	16	2896496	-0.00169	2.479653	0.2556	pLARmEB		20	34318166	-0.00127	3.622131	0.1235	pLARmEB
	16	33728133	0.001184	2.808394	0.1012	pLARmEB		20	42162207	0.001094	14.36976	0.0251	pLARmEB
	17	39450868	0.006009	3.180162	0.904464	ISIS-EMBLASSO	BS	18	1594961	-0.00193	2.387941	0.3288	pLARmEB
	17	38148531	-0.0069	3.338	1.5813	pKWmEB		18	3158152	0.001757	5.584138	0.2758	pLARmEB
	17	38314837	-0.01284	5.874854	0.03532	mrMLM		18	61292001	-0.00245	3.920478	0.4513	pLARmEB
	17	22752888	0.080007	3.550122	0.01048	FASTmrEMMA		20	45734650	0.016474	4.599755	4.193854	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	18	6705051	-0.05491	14.96909	11.15809	ISIS-EMBLASSO		20	45851691	-0.0088	3.4721	1.9281	pKWmEB
	18	6705051	3.11E-08	8.18E-02	0.013	GEMMA		20	45851691	-0.01168	5.670737	1.864202	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	18	6705051	-0.06558	16.17856	0.178939	mrMLM							

LR: main root length; LH: length of hypocotyls of healthy seedlings after treatments with control; FWR: the fresh weights of roots; DWR: dry weights of roots; BS: the biomass of seedlings.

Table S5. Significantly associated SNPs for five quantitative traits in Soybean datasets with salt treatment in 2015 using six GWAS methods

Trait	Chr	Position (bp)	Genome-wide association studies				Trait	Chr	Position (bp)	Genome-wide association studies			
			Effect	LOD	r ² (%)	Method				Effect	LOD	r ² (%)	Method
LR	2	47368397	0.3511	3.1501	0.0378	mrMLM	LH	1	51016651	0.2743	4.1759	2.4502	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	2	47368397	0.5218	2.8885	0.0217	FASTmrEMMA		2	14958573	-0.3549	4.8387	3.2944	pLARmEB
	2	47368397	0.0099	2.2416	0.0033	pLARmEB		2	14958573	-0.3841	5.3344	4.2086	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	3	3678366	0.7857	6.1884	15.5635	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	40464717	-6.11E-05	3.5972	6.50E-08	pKWmEB
	3	3678366	0.4679	3.3179	5.2925	pLARmEB		6	42784786	-0.5437	2.6687	0.0161	FASTmrEMMA
	4	8681502	-0.8441	6.1712	9.494	ISIS-EMBLASSO		6	42784786	-0.3004	3.2499	2.4666	pKWmEB
	4	6592821	-0.5919	3.5558	0.0586	mrMLM		7	35683968	0.3663	3.9627	4.1559	pKWmEB
	4	6592821	-0.0013	5.4692	0	pLARmEB		8	46830922	-0.7697	3.5041	0.0322	FASTmrEMMA
	6	44099223	-0.2869	2.9286	1.9222	ISIS-EMBLASSO		8	46830922	-0.445	3.9953	4.8798	pKWmEB
	6	46268901	0.3943	3.9328	0.0328	mrMLM		9	3532214	0.0033	5.0002	0.0002	pLARmEB
	6	46268901	0.7284	3.3804	0.028	FASTmrEMMA		9	20857215	0.846	4.6157	0.0453	FASTmrEMMA
	8	18890024	-0.2284	2.7032	1.6196	ISIS-EMBLASSO		9	42030427	0.4148	4.7412	0.0463	mrMLM
	8	19168401	-0.002	4.7103	0.0001	pLARmEB		9	3532214	0.347	3.5594	2.8119	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	10	3293836	-0.877	5.9205	6.8506	ISIS-EMBLASSO		9	20857215	0.4762	7.3445	6.5461	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	11	922317	-0.6916	5.0731	7.7448	ISIS-EMBLASSO		9	42030427	0.3143	4.9218	3.2324	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	11	922317	-0.4594	3.9336	3.2762	pLARmEB		12	25510360	0.6548	6.2638	12.7306	pLARmEB
	13	26197467	-0.3734	2.5126	1.5563	ISIS-EMBLASSO		12	25510360	0.7801	6.0884	0.1619	mrMLM
	13	11325848	0.0019	4.0947	0.0001	pLARmEB		12	25510360	0.8453	8.7278	23.1339	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	17	8125763	0.3529	4.4915	2.6316	pLARmEB		13	35215726	-0.4089	2.5778	2.1812	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	18	2214125	-1.5081	4.4358	0.091	mrMLM		14	4141733	-0.004	2.2857	0.0005	pLARmEB
	18	49219700	0.3591	4.0282	0.0369	mrMLM		14	7217735	0.3018	3.1096	0.0204	mrMLM
	18	2326242	-0.7686	3.6376	0.03	FASTmrEMMA		15	29713646	-0.8524	4.2661	0.0424	FASTmrEMMA
	20	3902250	-2.0258	7.6957	0.1643	mrMLM		16	31087981	0.4919	7.1356	7.3141	pLARmEB

FWR	1	4956870	0.0099	3.4411	0.0312	mrMLM		16	31087981	0.6218	2.7847	0.027	FASTmrEMMA
	1	4956870	0.0099	3.4411	0.0312	mrMLM		16	31087981	0.5157	4.1947	0.072	mrMLM
	1	469540	0.0011	2.6789	0.0397	pLARmEB		16	31087981	0.3207	4.3348	3.1927	pKWmEB
	1	581883	0.001	2.9494	0.0301	pLARmEB		16	31087981	0.5457	8.7466	9.8179	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	1	52602710	-0.0071	2.3372	3.199	pLARmEB		17	41528942	-0.6963	4.6372	0.092	mrMLM
	1	54828772	0.0019	3.082	0.0787	pLARmEB		17	41528942	-0.4764	3.2652	4.934	pKWmEB
	2	50505927	-0.0025	3.5644	0.1974	pKWmEB		17	8182950	0.3189	2.3842	1.8809	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	2	10674137	0.0325	7.6889	0.1607	mrMLM		17	39465089	-0.1985	2.6747	1.3015	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	2	10674137	0.0325	7.6889	0.1607	mrMLM		18	58287684	0.5659	2.5268	0.0173	FASTmrEMMA
	2	50963190	-0.0023	6.5577	0.2827	pLARmEB		18	58888896	0.5677	2.9623	0.0188	FASTmrEMMA
	3	45302035	0.0148	6.1422	3.0005	ISIS-EMBLASSO		18	2075424	0.4924	5.2207	0.0645	mrMLM
	3	45302035	0.0088	4.017	1.4018	pKWmEB		18	2036717	0.2098	2.914	1.536	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	3	29644613	0.0107	8.0105	0.0411	mrMLM		18	1888093	-0.2297	2.7541	1.4043	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	3	29644613	0.0107	8.0105	0.0411	mrMLM		18	7705143	-0.2367	3.8821	1.8465	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	3	20698296	-0.0019	4.483	0.0101	pLARmEB		18	39483932	0.6243	3.1393	5.0852	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	3	37977600	0.0018	2.2382	0.0958	pLARmEB		18	58888896	0.1969	2.0855	0.9057	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	4	37026887	0.0083	3.4887	0.0208	mrMLM		20	42627881	0.0013	2.9741	0	pLARmEB
	4	37026887	0.0083	3.4887	0.0208	mrMLM		20	46580394	1.0113	4.9599	0.0438	FASTmrEMMA
	4	40160663	-0.0264	2.5058	0.0224	FASTmrEMMA		20	46550252	0.337	4.0507	1.9927	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	5	1297851	-0.0059	2.1846	0.6085	ISIS-EMBLASSO	DWR	1	8468083	-0.0009	1.7411	0.6946	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	5	1073817	0.0031	5.3556	0.3068	pLARmEB		1	52600033	0.0004	1.846	0.2429	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	5	36248203	0.0017	2.5824	0.1207	pLARmEB		1	55634509	-0.0022	5.6994	2.0265	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	6	13121215	-0.0078	3.2575	1.7933	pKWmEB		1	32258279	5.80E-05	3.6438	0.0061	pKWmEB
	6	11900234	0.0101	3.6908	0.0254	mrMLM		1	32268757	3.53E-05	3.7043	0.0022	pKWmEB
	6	11900234	0.0101	3.6908	0.0254	mrMLM		2	7151199	0	2.1805	0.0042	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	6	5684385	-0.0012	3.4292	0.038	pLARmEB		2	36006298	0.0009	4.4178	1.1566	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	6	15695551	0.0011	4.2064	0.0499	pLARmEB		2	49744549	1.32E-05	12.9078	4.00E-04	pKWmEB

6	30631128	-0.0022	2.0617	0.1708	pLARmEB		2	49752397	3.58E-05	5.6541	0.0025	pKWmEB
7	6463073	-0.0109	6.4864	4.6466	pKWmEB		2	30024097	-6.07E-05	4.9153	0.0038	pKWmEB
7	6439407	-0.0086	4.5921	0.0276	mrMLM		2	8081554	4.79E-05	11.0166	0.0047	pKWmEB
7	6439407	-0.0086	4.5921	0.0276	mrMLM		2	8231903	5.37E-05	6.7461	0.006	pKWmEB
7	5331354	0.002	3.5097	0.252	pLARmEB		3	20993817	-0.0016	4.6239	1.7756	ISIS-EMBLASSO
7	8579088	-0.0207	2.5268	0.7774	pLARmEB		3	11713207	1.30E-07	1.33E-02	0.011	GEMMA
8	11330945	-0.0133	6.9273	4.6699	pKWmEB		3	34285550	-2.54E-05	5.154	5.00E-04	pKWmEB
8	11330945	-0.0097	3.8971	0.0245	mrMLM		3	21142646	3.00E-04	3.7616	0.0791	pKWmEB
8	11330945	-0.0097	3.8971	0.0245	mrMLM		3	29512697	-2.00E-04	4.5382	0.0354	pKWmEB
8	43335571	-0.0013	2.8138	0.074	pLARmEB		4	39515342	-0.0121	8.03	0.1646	mrMLM
9	41272866	-0.0067	2.164	0.7481	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	15624761	-0.0017	4.972	0.0124	mrMLM
9	43496689	0.0136	6.5679	3.2227	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	95173	-0.0039	3.5809	0.0576	mrMLM
9	43301721	-0.0169	4.5628	0.0541	mrMLM		4	3444068	0.0019	4.3931	1.0713	ISIS-EMBLASSO
9	42746053	0.0216	5.0713	0.0761	mrMLM		4	15624761	-0.0026	3.7805	2.7113	ISIS-EMBLASSO
9	43672146	-0.0059	4.4679	0.7676	pKWmEB		4	39255037	-0.0012	2.8485	1.2509	ISIS-EMBLASSO
9	2282229	-0.016	8.9327	6.2317	pLARmEB		4	39515342	-0.0061	2.661	3.743	ISIS-EMBLASSO
9	41272866	-0.0031	3.3678	0.5785	pLARmEB		4	36784958	5.34E-15	1.80E-02	0.019	GEMMA
9	44623052	0.001	2.0079	0.0138	pLARmEB		4	26315175	1.47E-12	1.50E-02	0.019	GEMMA
10	44119661	-0.0142	3.1203	2.5711	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	39515342	2.90E-12	1.53E-02	0.013	GEMMA
10	50739634	0.0218	7.01	5.0193	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	40739509	1.23E-11	1.25E-02	0.018	GEMMA
10	50739634	0.0274	6.0194	0.0863	mrMLM		4	27458987	2.93E-11	1.34E-02	0.021	GEMMA
10	7178841	-0.0325	4.3538	0.0303	mrMLM		4	23197832	4.31E-11	1.18E-02	0.022	GEMMA
10	3296125	-0.0195	4.993	0.0718	mrMLM		4	23197835	4.31E-11	1.18E-02	0.022	GEMMA
10	50739634	0.024	5.7831	8.16	pKWmEB		4	33071947	5.85E-11	1.38E-02	0.015	GEMMA
10	44119661	-0.008	3.8254	1.1003	pKWmEB		4	24960538	3.22E-10	1.08E-02	0.028	GEMMA
10	42618806	0.0097	3.492	0.0267	mrMLM		4	24715091	3.69E-10	1.14E-02	0.024	GEMMA
10	4218101	0.0093	3.8271	0.0159	mrMLM		4	27985177	4.99E-10	1.13E-02	0.023	GEMMA

10	42618806	0.0097	3.492	0.0267	mrMLM		4	25668253	5.03E-10	1.13E-02	0.023	GEMMA
10	4218101	0.0093	3.8271	0.0159	mrMLM		4	37081248	5.14E-10	1.13E-02	0.024	GEMMA
10	44119661	-0.0373	3.3402	0.0327	FASTmrEMMA		4	37081249	5.14E-10	1.13E-02	0.024	GEMMA
10	10330190	-0.0082	2.4312	0.1827	pLARmEB		4	21639107	5.26E-10	1.13E-02	0.023	GEMMA
11	11316463	-0.0123	4.1821	2.2792	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	25600881	5.26E-10	1.13E-02	0.023	GEMMA
11	5245829	-0.0102	3.8833	3.5818	pKWmEB		4	23206714	5.44E-10	1.12E-02	0.024	GEMMA
11	8085669	-0.0091	5.2044	0.0317	mrMLM		4	21714859	1.09E-09	1.13E-02	0.025	GEMMA
11	27803417	-0.0121	4.0956	0.0323	mrMLM		4	24163803	1.09E-09	1.13E-02	0.025	GEMMA
11	8085669	-0.0091	5.2044	0.0317	mrMLM		4	25183097	1.09E-09	1.13E-02	0.025	GEMMA
11	27803417	-0.0121	4.0956	0.0323	mrMLM		4	25209767	1.17E-09	1.05E-02	0.027	GEMMA
11	922317	-0.0064	2.3507	1.1571	pLARmEB		4	25209768	1.17E-09	1.05E-02	0.027	GEMMA
11	922322	-0.0078	3.507	1.6581	pLARmEB		4	37026856	1.20E-09	1.12E-02	0.025	GEMMA
11	1606205	0.0036	9.6013	0.7593	pLARmEB		4	36044495	1.34E-09	1.26E-02	0.015	GEMMA
11	18530193	0.0023	2.6547	0.2016	pLARmEB		4	36785020	1.39E-09	1.05E-02	0.024	GEMMA
11	33075627	0.0033	2.208	0.5875	pLARmEB		4	24632609	2.45E-09	9.70E-03	0.024	GEMMA
13	5660505	0.0216	2.9041	4.632	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	24632617	2.45E-09	9.70E-03	0.024	GEMMA
13	5660505	5.00E-04	3.766	0.003	pKWmEB		4	23045530	3.14E-09	9.63E-03	0.024	GEMMA
13	38098734	0.0247	4.0363	0.0238	FASTmrEMMA		4	24118705	1.85E-08	9.01E-03	0.027	GEMMA
13	12538464	-0.0034	6.2665	0.3578	pLARmEB		4	23045554	1.99E-08	8.69E-03	0.036	GEMMA
13	22544267	-0.0023	4.5222	0.3186	pLARmEB		4	25365786	2.33E-08	9.14E-03	0.025	GEMMA
13	30845044	-0.0013	4.4821	0.0618	pLARmEB		4	25094747	2.47E-08	9.11E-03	0.026	GEMMA
13	38098734	0.0013	2.3591	0.1112	pLARmEB		4	20464127	2.54E-08	9.12E-03	0.026	GEMMA
14	49216727	-0.0076	2.793	0.8094	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	25454475	2.64E-08	8.99E-03	0.032	GEMMA
14	6376701	-0.0149	4.7106	4.0882	pKWmEB		4	24470360	7.04E-08	8.96E-03	0.043	GEMMA
14	6376701	-0.0167	5.967	0.0502	mrMLM		4	36044497	7.21E-08	8.73E-03	0.029	GEMMA
14	6376701	-0.0167	5.967	0.0502	mrMLM		4	37005487	9.91E-08	7.96E-03	0.043	GEMMA
14	6431847	0.002	3.9344	0.1426	pLARmEB		4	15624761	1.89E-07	7.45E-03	0.047	GEMMA

15	47621167	0.0109	4.0022	1.8404	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	19717905	1.99E-07	7.61E-03	0.037	GEMMA
15	47621167	0.0173	4.7877	0.0506	mrMLM		4	36980153	2.06E-07	7.83E-03	0.045	GEMMA
15	930751	-0.0048	4.4661	0.5872	pKWmEB		4	23669225	-7.93E-05	8.3055	0.0041	pKWmEB
15	22784679	-0.0012	2.8111	0.0949	pLARmEB		4	19717905	-2.00E-04	3.3841	0.0165	pKWmEB
16	34717726	0.0081	2.2528	0.8433	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	47809944	2.53E-05	5.4417	0.0012	pKWmEB
16	36445493	0.0029	3.6117	0.5185	pLARmEB		4	22218893	-1.27E-05	4.2591	1.00E-04	pKWmEB
17	38650676	-0.0093	2.8748	1.452	ISIS-EMBLASSO		4	40938029	2.00E-04	8.4897	0.0831	pKWmEB
17	38650676	-0.0094	3.4267	2.0113	pKWmEB		5	19260807	7.01E-09	1.51E-02	0.011	GEMMA
17	9590915	-0.01	5.3542	0.0378	mrMLM		5	39881445	1.41E-05	6.5233	4.00E-04	pKWmEB
17	15319513	0.0073	3.1957	0.0198	mrMLM		5	8035158	-1.08E-05	4.3378	5.81E-05	pKWmEB
17	9590915	-0.01	5.3542	0.0378	mrMLM		5	7004778	-6.00E-04	17.0388	0.3476	pKWmEB
17	15319513	0.0073	3.1957	0.0198	mrMLM		6	3199037	-0.0054	3.4381	0.0645	mrMLM
17	40687790	0.0235	3.001	0.0217	FASTmrEMMA		6	37636945	2.40E-08	1.12E-02	0.016	GEMMA
17	5082689	0.0012	7.2194	0.024	pLARmEB		6	13136190	3.32E-08	1.43E-02	0.011	GEMMA
18	58287684	0.0125	2.6595	1.5412	ISIS-EMBLASSO		6	38300614	1.38E-07	1.10E-02	0.022	GEMMA
18	59563278	-0.0405	4.3264	4.7276	ISIS-EMBLASSO		6	12859150	-7.00E-04	6.5342	0.731	pKWmEB
18	58888896	6.87E-05	4.4668	7.83E-05	pKWmEB		6	6081361	5.36E-05	3.6517	0.005	pKWmEB
18	49219700	9.00E-04	3.3187	0.0179	pKWmEB		7	11225530	0.0012	4.4188	0.0251	mrMLM
18	58283890	0.0019	3.6701	0.0607	pKWmEB		7	8205660	-0.0036	8.2949	7.4107	ISIS-EMBLASSO
18	6705051	-0.0396	8.8735	0.0834	mrMLM		7	40115668	-0.002	6.0194	4.922	ISIS-EMBLASSO
18	1242253	-0.0153	7.4953	0.0414	mrMLM		7	8047526	-1.39E-05	4.2468	2.00E-04	pKWmEB
18	18004860	0.0127	3.4742	0.0503	mrMLM		7	11003570	4.54E-05	3.4287	0.0041	pKWmEB
18	6705051	-0.0396	8.8735	0.0834	mrMLM		7	11002715	2.41E-05	9.627	0.0012	pKWmEB
18	1242253	-0.0153	7.4953	0.0414	mrMLM		7	22207435	-1.45E-05	3.8913	4.00E-04	pKWmEB
18	18004860	0.0127	3.4742	0.0503	mrMLM		7	22922860	-1.17E-05	3.6896	2.00E-04	pKWmEB
18	58287684	0.0356	4.7178	0.0325	FASTmrEMMA		7	23064544	-1.04E-05	10.0499	2.00E-04	pKWmEB
19	2445201	-0.0166	3.8729	0.0372	mrMLM		7	38255339	1.19E-05	4.6006	2.00E-04	pKWmEB

	19	2445201	-0.0166	3.8729	0.0372	mrMLM		8	9660436	0.00331	3.08229	0.02237	FASTmrEMMA
	19	631442	-0.0012	5.261	0.0238	pLARMmEB		8	9595077	-0.0028	4.1799	4.6749	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	19	44854583	-0.0079	4.4058	3.4526	pLARMmEB		9	7266512	0.0014	3.3547	0.0389	mrMLM
	20	37616538	-0.0082	4.8564	2.6055	pKWmEB		9	43184955	3.98E-09	1.43E-02	0.011	GEMMA
	20	45057341	-0.0011	2.4533	0.0722	pLARMmEB		9	39771589	3.26E-08	1.09E-02	0.025	GEMMA
BS	1	4575182	-0.0175	5.9678	3.0412	ISIS-EMBLASSO		9	1459471	7.73E-08	1.29E-02	0.017	GEMMA
	1	674489	0.0227	2.7928	0.0146	FASTmrEMMA		9	39755700	1.60E-07	8.55E-03	0.027	GEMMA
	1	5813393	0.0157	3.0688	0.0162	FASTmrEMMA		9	36583814	2.20E-07	1.05E-02	0.015	GEMMA
	1	55375068	-0.0156	2.9779	0.0083	FASTmrEMMA		9	43672155	1.60E-05	3.7583	5.00E-04	pKWmEB
	1	674489	0.0016	2.4662	0.0296	pLARMmEB		9	45674783	1.22E-05	3.1716	3.00E-04	pKWmEB
	1	55375068	-0.0034	2.7641	0.2989	pLARMmEB		9	37043022	1.99E-05	5.3379	6.00E-04	pKWmEB
	1	4575182	-0.002	3.417	0.1932	pLARMmEB		10	44557773	-0.00556	5.22397	0.0596	FASTmrEMMA
	2	10674137	0.0159	2.8646	2.9423	ISIS-EMBLASSO		10	17675230	7.24E-09	1.52E-02	0.011	GEMMA
	2	50826684	-0.0081	3.3628	1.4011	ISIS-EMBLASSO		10	16563811	7.90E-09	1.51E-02	0.011	GEMMA
	2	4500068	-0.002	2.2529	0.0883	pLARMmEB		10	11654011	1.08E-07	1.30E-02	0.013	GEMMA
	2	50515905	-0.0016	2.973	0.2963	pLARMmEB		11	16176924	0.0016	3.8866	2.3995	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	3	39337177	0.0012	2.2372	0.2777	pLARMmEB		11	16264839	1.35E-05	3.3967	3.00E-04	pKWmEB
	3	6328659	-0.0014	3.0759	0.3385	pLARMmEB		11	16346023	1.30E-05	5.0623	3.00E-04	pKWmEB
	4	5508478	0.0043	2.3651	0.254	ISIS-EMBLASSO		12	18040412	5.86E-11	1.38E-02	0.014	GEMMA
	4	9712279	0.0115	7.7863	3.7157	ISIS-EMBLASSO		13	40691773	0.0014	4.9058	2.5308	ISIS-EMBLASSO
	4	9631962	-0.0226	6.1851	0.0336	FASTmrEMMA		13	5660515	2.22E-05	6.0941	6.00E-04	pKWmEB
	5	771731	4.57E-10	8.71E-02	0.013	GEMMA		13	40691773	4.03E-05	6.9407	0.0024	pKWmEB
	5	31575389	0.1023	8.938	0.046	FASTmrEMMA		13	21832469	1.24E-05	8.9708	3.00E-04	pKWmEB
	5	38166911	0.0012	2.2797	0.1391	pLARMmEB		13	34336105	-0.0016	12.2155	0.5085	pKWmEB
	5	6814620	0.0012	2.756	0.5769	pLARMmEB		13	22492515	2.00E-04	5.2456	0.0552	pKWmEB
	5	22177076	0.006	3.7498	0.2497	pLARMmEB		13	13725217	4.71E-05	6.0717	0.0015	pKWmEB
	5	35651707	-0.0019	4.5502	0.0588	pLARMmEB		13	21832449	1.22E-05	8.7016	3.00E-04	pKWmEB

6	29286345	0.001	2.119	0.1738	pLARmEB		14	3954241	2.81E-05	5.6215	0.0014	pKWmEB
7	2535953	-0.0051	2.6841	0.5716	ISIS-EMBLASSO		14	2005374	5.57E-05	5.5043	0.0048	pKWmEB
7	6463073	-0.0072	5.4146	1.5076	ISIS-EMBLASSO		15	10761565	0.0238	4.3733	0.064	mrMLM
7	14760421	-0.0373	7.1169	4.007	ISIS-EMBLASSO		15	3686962	-0.0008	1.8202	0.4817	ISIS-EMBLASSO
7	14292812	8.21E-08	9.35E-02	0.013	GEMMA		15	15793353	0.0021	4.7143	6.1879	ISIS-EMBLASSO
7	14760421	1.20E-07	7.29E-02	0.016	GEMMA		15	3724342	1.70E-07	6.46E-03	0.058	GEMMA
7	14760422	1.20E-07	7.29E-02	0.016	GEMMA		15	47621191	1.25E-05	7.6736	3.00E-04	pKWmEB
7	5601401	-0.0184	3.2583	0.0128	FASTmrEMMA		15	3262318	-0.0015	8.116	2.1481	pKWmEB
7	6439407	-0.0244	6.8711	0.0382	FASTmrEMMA		16	31903629	-0.0001	2.2843	0.0079	ISIS-EMBLASSO
7	6929245	-0.0027	2.1254	0.2848	pLARmEB		16	31024338	2.09E-09	1.36E-02	0.011	GEMMA
7	35727264	-0.0018	4.4508	0.9534	pLARmEB		16	31118222	2.13E-09	1.35E-02	0.011	GEMMA
7	2535953	-0.0019	4.7298	0.6275	pLARmEB		16	33667312	4.00E-04	7.6924	0.295	pKWmEB
7	5601401	-0.0058	7.0554	0.3457	pLARmEB		16	28447572	-2.00E-04	8.3251	0.0639	pKWmEB
8	11330945	-0.0087	5.5664	1.4986	ISIS-EMBLASSO		16	25697414	1.00E-04	4.4953	0.0357	pKWmEB
8	17248047	0.0023	2.0568	0.7203	pLARmEB		16	6265535	-5.78E-05	4.6855	0.0052	pKWmEB
8	11931046	-0.0012	2.7066	0.5644	pLARmEB		17	38650597	0.0027	2.90589	0.0275	FASTmrEMMA
8	13564732	0.003	4.0025	0.2341	pLARmEB		17	37958839	-0.0024	4.9593	2.7365	ISIS-EMBLASSO
9	3532214	0.0044	3.03	0.4103	ISIS-EMBLASSO		17	38650597	0.0006	2.1196	0.597	ISIS-EMBLASSO
9	8039762	-0.0367	4.4677	0.0245	FASTmrEMMA		17	12789281	-1.45E-05	5.7259	2.00E-04	pKWmEB
9	40560138	0.0013	2.3106	1.8907	pLARmEB		18	25758217	2.90E-09	1.00E-02	0.022	GEMMA
9	43496689	0.002	2.5696	0.4924	pLARmEB		18	2705706	3.52E-09	1.35E-02	0.022	GEMMA
9	4245195	-0.0021	2.7135	0.0989	pLARmEB		18	26951439	1.48E-08	8.62E-03	0.044	GEMMA
10	42750933	0.0108	7.4551	2.9057	ISIS-EMBLASSO		18	26276804	1.50E-08	1.07E-02	0.016	GEMMA
10	48465013	0.0059	3.5714	0.9544	ISIS-EMBLASSO		18	26946257	2.77E-08	9.08E-03	0.025	GEMMA
10	6256342	-0.0112	2.9172	0.0084	FASTmrEMMA		18	49158018	0.001	3.2344	1.2275	ISIS-EMBLASSO
11	5245829	-0.0096	7.6083	2.355	ISIS-EMBLASSO		18	49219700	8.23E-05	7.8262	0.0126	pKWmEB
11	11121307	-0.0051	2.1334	0.4685	ISIS-EMBLASSO		18	49182403	1.27E-05	7.4647	2.00E-04	pKWmEB

11	5245829	-0.0149	2.6024	0.0135	FASTmrEMMA		18	26820280	-1.77E-05	8.4014	3.00E-04	pKWmEB
11	8085669	-0.0163	3.6178	0.0167	FASTmrEMMA		18	16378841	3.36E-05	3.0815	0.0023	pKWmEB
11	5720476	-0.0015	2.0436	0.1973	pLARmEB		18	48892414	1.32E-05	4.4888	3.00E-04	pKWmEB
11	38682012	-0.0017	5.3982	0.2697	pLARmEB		18	26951439	-3.00E-04	3.2704	0.0547	pKWmEB
12	3523573	1.08E-07	7.67E-02	0.013	GEMMA		18	1060630	1.11E-05	3.8476	2.00E-04	pKWmEB
12	3507039	1.86E-07	8.45E-02	0.017	GEMMA		18	17218282	-1.03E-05	4.0576	1.00E-04	pKWmEB
12	3507065	1.86E-07	8.45E-02	0.017	GEMMA		18	2040047	1.39E-05	4.1252	3.00E-04	pKWmEB
12	34894949	-0.0135	2.8434	0.0105	FASTmrEMMA		18	58759499	3.91E-05	6.4116	0.0026	pKWmEB
12	34514905	-0.0019	6.3573	0.3637	pLARmEB		18	59000963	2.00E-04	11.1385	0.1069	pKWmEB
13	42403452	-0.0119	5.9992	2.4821	ISIS-EMBLASSO		19	44854583	-0.0218	4.677	7.1841	ISIS-EMBLASSO
13	21079646	1.79E-09	9.88E-02	0.011	GEMMA		19	12180109	8.14E-05	6.6943	0.006	pKWmEB
13	20704079	1.55E-08	9.23E-02	0.011	GEMMA		19	9567108	-1.25E-05	3.8069	1.00E-04	pKWmEB
13	6758368	-0.0011	2.5506	0.6332	pLARmEB		19	39550435	-1.26E-05	4.3828	3.00E-04	pKWmEB
13	12628631	-0.0013	4.6216	0.1682	pLARmEB		19	39259035	7.44E-05	4.3879	0.0115	pKWmEB
14	1528136	0.0058	4.0819	0.7846	ISIS-EMBLASSO		20	2392724	0.0076	2.4286	1.0025	ISIS-EMBLASSO
14	6376701	-0.0091	3.6097	1.1353	ISIS-EMBLASSO		20	42855508	7.25E-08	1.08E-02	0.036	GEMMA
14	45165579	1.60E-08	7.54E-02	0.022	GEMMA		20	33174686	-0.0021	5.1956	2.9488	ISIS-EMBLASSO
14	1175148	-0.0012	2.3932	0.1825	pLARmEB		20	40611745	3.00E-04	5.0937	0.2445	pKWmEB
14	6376701	-0.0019	2.6458	0.1736	pLARmEB		20	254800	-1.53E-05	3.2826	3.00E-04	pKWmEB
14	10032189	0.0015	2.66	0.7421	pLARmEB		20	40611745	0.0011	5.1039	2.1076	ISIS-EMBLASSO
15	11051359	-0.0062	4.7141	1.0568	ISIS-EMBLASSO	BS	18	61136227	-0.0013	2.3724	0.5165	pLARmEB
15	35034544	-0.0297	7.2091	2.1857	ISIS-EMBLASSO		19	618515	-0.0082	6.1226	1.7503	ISIS-EMBLASSO
15	15793353	0.0037	3.3973	0.018	pLARmEB		19	6342507	0	2.143	0	ISIS-EMBLASSO
15	48115929	0.0026	4.5214	0.1361	pLARmEB		19	39213907	0.0111	11.5188	3.5502	ISIS-EMBLASSO
16	27603247	-0.0042	3.0777	0.4923	ISIS-EMBLASSO		19	45435168	1.85E-07	8.19E-02	0.013	GEMMA
17	9590915	-0.003	2.6044	0.2564	ISIS-EMBLASSO		19	1998758	-0.0019	2.5129	4.5845	pLARmEB
17	8760885	0.0011	2.0185	0.2361	pLARmEB		19	39191055	0.0016	2.6552	1.2094	pLARmEB

17	11602669	-0.0013	2.4806	0.3911	pLARmEB		19	41150744	0.0031	3.4186	0.1565	pLARmEB
18	18004860	0.0084	4.4233	1.6912	ISIS-EMBLASSO		19	830622	0.0022	4.0092	1.6324	pLARmEB
18	6705051	5.96E-09	8.01E-02	0.013	GEMMA		20	45832145	-0.0081	6.3361	1.9152	ISIS-EMBLASSO
18	56716258	6.04E-09	8.41E-02	0.016	GEMMA		20	32695468	1.42E-08	7.89E-02	0.015	GEMMA

LR: main root length; LH: length of hypocotyls of healthy seedlings after treatments with control; FWR: the fresh weights of roots; DWR: dry weights of roots; BS: the biomass of seedlings.

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